

Scuttle flies (Diptera: Phoridae) of Vitosha Mt (Bulgaria)

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Abstract: Two hundred and one species of the family have been established on the territory of the Vitosha Mt. The genera *Gymnoptera*, *Peromitra*, *Plectanocnema* and *Tubicera* have been recorded for the first time on the Balkan Peninsula and *Menoziola* – in Bulgaria. Sixty-nine species are new for the Balkan Peninsula and additional thirty-two – for Bulgaria. On the basis of the established number of species, it can be concluded that Vitosha Mountain is an area with a significant scuttle fly diversity. Some new data are established about flower visiting of some scuttle fly species.

Keywords: Balkan Peninsula, Bulgaria, flower visiting, new data, Phoridae, Vitosha Mt

Introduction

Vitosha Mt is located in southwestern Bulgaria, south of Sofia – between 42°28' and 42°40' N and 23°10' and 23°22' E, and belongs to the Kraishite-Srednogorie mountain system. It is surrounded by the Pernik Kettle (750 m above sea level), Sofia Kettle (550 m) and Samokov Kettle (1000 m) and the low mountains Lyulin, Verila and Plana, with which it has an orographic connection through the saddles – Vladaya (860 m), Buka-Prezlap (1090 m) and Yarema – 1195 m. All this has a certain impact on the microclimatic conditions in the corresponding parts of the mountain. The dimensions of the mountain are about 23 km long and 19 km wide, its area is 27800 ha (278 km²) and represents 0.25% of the territory of Bulgaria. Highest peak is Cherni Vruh – 2290 m.

Above 1000 species of scuttle flies are described from the Palaearctic Region, most of them – from Europe. In Bulgaria, 130 species are known up to now. The new taxa for Bulgaria are marked with one asterisk (*) and for the Balkan Peninsula – with two asterisks (**). All materials are deposited in the author's collection at the National Museum of Natural History, Bulgarian Academy of Sciences, Sofia.

Material and methods

The material has been collected by combining transects and stationary methods. Stationary methods were represented by different types of traps (Malaise trap, pitfall traps and traps in tree crowns) and entomological net. The traps are white conical plastic cups with a base diameter of 65 mm, an opening of 88 mm and a height of 118 mm. 4% formalin was used as a fixative with some detergent. Here we use the name “soil traps” for the pitfall traps and “tree trap” for those hanged on the branches of the trees. Part of the material was collected by MSS traps (“milieu souterrain superficiel”, published already in Langourov et al., 2014).

Collecting sites

– Northern part

Deciduous forest belt (mixed and beech forests). Composed mainly of *Corylus avellana* L., *Carpinus betulus* L. and with participation of *Quercus dalechampii* Ten., *Fagus sylvatica* L., *Betula pendula* Roth, *Sambucus nigra* L. The grass cover is composed mainly of different species of *Poa*, *Festuca*, *Bromus*, *Phleum*, as well

as *Anemone ranunculoides* L., *Allium ursinum* L., *Heleborus odoratus* W. et K., *Corydalis* sp., *Erythronium dens-canis* L.

[N1.01] above Simeonovo Suburb, 820 m a.s.l.

[N1.02] near Boyana Suburb, 850–870 m a.s.l.

[N1.03] above Boyana Suburb, 1080 m a.s.l.

[N1.04] above Boyana Lake, 1260 m a.s.l.

[N1.05] E of Kopitoto Peak, 1350 m a.s.l.

[N1.06] Kirova Livada Place, 1360 m a.s.l.

[N1.07] near Kamen Del Chalet, 1470 m a.s.l.

Spruce forest belt. The lower floor of these spruce forests is built mainly of *Rubus idaeus* L. and with the participation of a number of cereal grasses – *Calamagrostis* sp., *Elymus* sp. [N2.03]: *Pinus peuce* Griseb. forest with undergrowth of *Arctostaphylos uva-ursi* (L.) Spreng. and *Vaccinium* sp.

[N2.01] near Bor Chalet, 1600 m a.s.l.

[N2.02] near Tintyava Chalet, 1650 m a.s.l.

[N2.03] Gyoreva Cheshma Spring, 1750 m a.s.l.

Subalpine zone. Acidophilic psychrophytic grass associations – in these formations the largest areas are occupied by *Nardus stricta* L., *Festuca valida* (R. Uechtr.) Pénzes, *Poa* sp., *Agrostis capillaris* L. and *Sesleria comosa* Velen. [N3.04]: the vegetation is of hygropsychrophilic (peatbog) type, which is characterised by the dominance of *Nardus stricta* and the presence of a number of co-dominants – *Potentilla erecta* Rausch., *Carex* spp., *Deschampsia caespitosa* (L.) P. Beauv., *Sphagnum* sp., with the participation of *Veratrum lobelianum* Bernh. and shrubs of *Salix lapponum* L.

[N3.01] near Kamen Del Peak, 1840 m a.s.l.

[N3.02] Petrov Grob Place, 1850 m a.s.l., (with scattered trees of *Pinus peuce*)

[N3.03] Ushite Peak, 1906 m a.s.l.

[N3.04] Torfeno Branishte Reserve – Kapaklivets Place, 1860 m a.s.l.

– Eastern part

Beech forest belt. In this part of the mountain are located some of the best preserved beech forests. The beech forests in [E1.03] are highly enlightened and there is no undergrowth, as the grass cover is dominated by *Luzula* sp. In [E1.02] the co-dominant of beech is *Alnus glutinosa* (L.) Gaertn. In all other sites in the undergrowth *Euonymus latifolius* (L.) Mill is found which is dominant in the lower floor of [E1.04] and [E1.05], *Rosa* sp., *Rubus* sp. and single specimens of *Sorbus aucuparia* L., *Viburnum opulus* L., *Crataegus*

monogyna Jacq., *Corylus avellana*. The grass cover is with the participation of *Poa nemoralis* L., *Digitalis* sp., *Lunaria* sp., and around the upper border of this belt there are *Galium odoratum* (L.) Scop. and *Luzula sylvatica* (Huds.) Gaudin.

[E1.01] Byala Voda Place near Yarema Saddle, 1130 m a.s.l.

[E1.02] near Gurgulitsa River, near Zheleznitsa Village, 1140 m a.s.l.

[E1.03] above Zheleznitsa Village, near Bukite Peak, 1200 m a.s.l.

[E1.04] above Bistritsa Village, 1200 m a.s.l.

[E1.05] near Bistritsa River, above Bistritsa Village, 1270 m a.s.l.

[E1.06] Bistrishko Branishte Reserve, near Bistritsa River, 1400 m a.s.l.

Spruce forest belt. Here are located one of the best preserved spruce forests within the mountain, for the protection of which was created one of the oldest nature reserves in Bulgaria and on the Balkans – “Bistrishko Branishte” (founded in 1934). The spruce forests in this part are centuries-old (over 150 years) monodominant, with the participation of single trees of *Abies alba* Mill. and *Pinus sylvestris* L., and the lower floor is mainly of *Luzula sylvatica*, *Festuca* sp., *Geranium* sp., *Oxalis acetosella* L. and scattered specimens of *Rubus idaeus* and *Doronicum columnae* Ten. Near the upper border of the belt the trees are thinning and the undergrowth is mainly of *Juniperus communis* ssp. *alpina* (Suter) Celak. and *Vaccinium myrtillus* L., which in the highest parts grow alone.

[E2.01] Bistrishko Branishte Reserve – Golyamata Gramada Place, 1550 m a.s.l.

[E2.02] Bistrishko Branishte Reserve – N of Golyamata Gramada Place, 1620 m a.s.l.

[E2.03] Bistrishko Branishte Reserve – Prisoite Place, 1750 m a.s.l.

Subalpine zone. Acidophilic psychrophytic grass associations – the largest areas are occupied by *Festuca valida*, *Poa* sp., *Agrostis capillaris* L., *Bruckenthalia spiculifolia* (Salisb.) Rchb., *Vaccinium* spp., *Salix waldsteiniana* Willd. and in [E3.02] is situated one of the largest communities of dwarf pine (*Pinus mugo* Turra) within the mountain.

[E3.01] Belcheva Skala Peak, 1831 m a.s.l. (limestone)

[E3.02] above Aleko Chalet, 1900 m a.s.l.

[E3.03] Bistrishko Branishte Reserve – Golyam Kupen Peak, 1930 m a.s.l.

[E3.04] near Malak Rezen Peak, 2150 m a.s.l.

– Western part

Mixed forest belt. The locality is in an aspen forest (*Populus tremula* L.) with participation of *Carpinus betulus*, *Corylus avellana*, *Betula pendula* and *Sambucus nigra*. The grass cover is composed mainly of different species of *Poa*, *Festuca*, *Bromus*, *Phleum*, as well as *Anemone ranunculoides*, *Allium ursinum*, *Heleborus odorus*, *Corydalis* sp., *Erytronium dens-canis*.

[W1.01] near Matnitsa River, 1000 m a.s.l.

Spruce belt. The spruce forests in this part are sparse with participation of *Fagus sylvatica* and *Betula pendula* and the lower floor is mainly of *Luzula sylvatica*, *Festuca* sp., *Rubus idaeus*.

[W2.01] near Ostritsa Chalet, 1650 m a.s.l.

Subalpine zone. [W3.01]: acidophilic psychrophytic grass formations with the participation of *Chamaecytisus* sp., *Luzula* sp., *Carex* sp., *J. communis* ssp. *alpina*, *Arctostaphylos uva-ursi* and single specimens of *Rubus idaeus*. [W3.02] and [W3.03]: the vegetation is of hygropsychrophilic (peatbog) type, which is characterised by the dominance of *Nardus stricta* and the presence of a number of co-dominants – *Potentilla erecta*, different species of *Carex*, *Sphagnum*, with the participation of *Luzula* sp., *Alchemilla* sp. and shrubs of *Salix lapponum* L. and *J. communis* ssp. *alpina*. [W3.04–06] are characterised by the alpine appearance of the vegetation cover: *N. stricta*, *Sesleria comosa*, *Festuca valida*, *F. nigrescens* Lam., *Poa media* Schur., *P. annua* L., *Agrostis capillaris*.

[W3.01] Konyarnika Place, 1870 m a.s.l.

[W3.02] Choveshki Kosti Place, 1950 m a.s.l.

[W3.03] Torfeno Branishte Reserve – Tri Kladentsi Place, 2020 m a.s.l.

[W3.04] Selimitsa Peak, 2041 m a.s.l.

[W3.05] Torfeno Branishte Reserve – Samara Peak, 2108 m a.s.l.

[W3.06] near Vurla River, 2150 m a.s.l.

– Southern part

Mixed forest belt. The locality is composed mainly of *Quercus frainetto* Ten. and *Quercus dalechampii* with the participation of *Crataegus monogyna*, *Carpinus betulus*, *Corylus avellana*. The grass cover is mainly of different species of *Poa*, *Festuca*, *Bromus*, *Phleum*, as well as *Anemone ranunculoides*.

[S1.01] near Bosnek Village, 940 m a.s.l.

Beech forest belt. The beech forests in this part of the mountain have been heavily exploited in the past

and currently consist of younger sparse beech trees with the participation of other tree and shrub species. Around the lower border of the belt there are *Carpinus betulus*, *Corylus avellana*, *Cornus mas* L., and around its upper border (which for this part is the upper border of the forest due to increased anthropogenic intervention in the past) – *Juniperus communis* ssp. *alpina*. Due to the low density of these forests, the grass cover is diverse, with a predominance of *Poa nemoralis*, *Digitalis* sp., *Lunaria* sp. and around the upper border are found *Asperula* sp., *Luzula sylvatica*.

[S2.01] Ribni Dol Place, 1240 m a.s.l.

Spruce belt. In this part of the mountain over 1600 m the forest has been almost completely destroyed, as in some places single coniferous trees and bushes have been preserved, and in the river valleys – *Alnus viridis* (Chaix) DC. with participation of *Fagus sylvatica* as the lower floor is mainly of *Luzula sylvatica*, *Festuca* sp., *Rubus idaeus*.

Subalpine zone. Acidophilic psychrophytic grass formations with the participation of a number of alpine elements – *Sesleria comosa*, *Festuca valida*, *F. nigrescens*, *Poa media*, *Agrostis rupestris* All., *Juncus trifidus* L., *Alopecurus gerardii* Vill., *Crocus veluchensis* Herb., *Dianthus micropis* Boiss.

[S4.01] Chernoto Plato Place, 2050 m a.s.l.

[S4.02] Yarlovski Kuppen Peak, 2173 m a.s.l.

[S4.03] near Cherni Vruh Peak, 2200 m a.s.l.

[S4.04] Cherni Vruh Peak, 2280 m a.s.l.

Results

Aenigmatiinae

1. *Aenigmatias franzi* Schmitz, 1950 – Material examined: [E3.01] soil traps: 7.VIII–6.IX.1999, 1 ♂ • [W3.02] soil traps: 3.VII–7.VIII.1999, 2 ♂♂ • [W3.03] soil traps: 3.VII–7.VIII.1999, 1 ♂. Palearctic species, known from Europe (Austria, Switzerland, Czech Republic, Great Britain) and Asia (Mongolia). For the Balkan Peninsula reported from Bulgaria and Montenegro (Langourov, 2009). Other localities in Bulgaria: Central Stara Planina Mts and Pirin Mts (Langourov, 2009).

2. *Aenigmatias lubbocki* (Verrall, 1877) – Material examined: [S1.01] Malaise trap: 4–10.VIII.1998, 5 ♂♂; 18–28.VIII.1998, 1 ♂; 28.VIII–4.IX.1998, 1 ♂; 29.VII–10.VIII.1999, 4 ♂♂, 2 ♀♀. Palearctic species, known from Europe and Asia (China). Other localities

in Bulgaria: Central Stara Planina Mts (Langourov, 2009).

Phorinae

** 3. *Anevrina curvinervis* (Becker, 1901) – Material examined: [N1.01] Malaise trap: 10–18.V.1997, 2 ♂♂; 28.IV–1.V.1998, 1 ♂. Holarctic species, known from Middle and North Europe and North America. New region: Balkan Peninsula – Bulgaria.

4. *Anevrina thoracica* (Meigen, 1804) – Material examined: [N1.03]: 30.V.1993, 1 ♂ • [E1.05] soil traps: 1.VIII–1.IX.1998, 3 ♂♂; 1.IX–1.X.1998, 1 ♂; 1.V–1.VI.1999, 1 ♀; 1.VIII–1.IX.1999, 5 ♂♂; 1.IX–1.X.1999, 1 ♂ • [N1.05] Malaise trap: 19–26.VI.1998, 1 ♂ • [N1.06] soil traps: 1.VII–1.VIII.1998, 1 ♂; 1.VIII–1.IX.1998, 2 ♂♂ • [E2.01]: 1.VIII–1.IX.1998, 4 ♂♂, soil traps; 1.VII–1.VIII.1999, 1 ♀, tree traps; 1.VIII–1.IX.1999, 1 ♂, tree traps; 1 ♂, soil traps • [N3.02]: 4.VII–6.VIII.1999, 4 ♂♂ • [E3.02]: 1.VI–1.VII.1999, 1 ♂, tree traps; 1.VII–1.VIII.1999, 1 ♂, soil traps • [W3.03] soil traps: 12.VI–3.VII.1999, 1 ♂. Holarctic; known from Europe and North America. Reported from Croatia (Langhoffer, 1919) and Montenegro (Langourov, 2004a). Other localities in Bulgaria: Osogovska Mt (Beschovski & Langourov, 1997).

* 5. *Anevrina unispinosa* (Zetterstedt, 1860) – Material examined: [E1.05] soil traps: 1.VIII–1.IX.1998, 1 ♂ • [N1.05] Malaise trap: 29.V–5.VI.1998, 1 ♂ • [N1.06] soil traps: 1.VI–1.VII.1999, 1 ♂. Palaearctic-Oriental species, known from Europe, Asia (Japan) and Oriental Region (Myanmar). For the Balkan Peninsula reported from Montenegro (Langourov, 2004a).

6. *Anevrina urbana* (Meigen, 1830) – Material examined: [N1.01] Malaise trap: 10–18.V.1997, 7 ♂♂ • [S1.01] Malaise trap: 3–17.IV.1999, 1 ♂; 17–30.IV.1999, 3 ♂♂. Holarctic species, known from Europe, Asia (Western Siberia) and North America. For the Balkan Peninsula reported from Croatia (Becker, 1901). Other localities in Bulgaria: Sofia Plain and Western Rhodope Mts (Langourov, 2004b, 2010).

7. *Borophaga irregularis* (Wood, 1912) – Material examined: [E1.04]: 27.VIII.1992, 1 ♂ • [E1.05] soil traps: 1.VIII–1.IX.1999, 1 ♂ • [N1.06]: 1.IX–1.X.1999, 3 ♂♂, soil traps; 1.IX–1.X.1999, 1 ♀, tree traps. European species. Published for the mountain by Beschovski & Langourov (1997).

* 8. *Chaetopleurophora bohemanii* (Becker, 1901) – Material examined: [N1.05] Malaise trap:

29.V–5.VI.1998, 1 ♂. European species, known for the Balkan Peninsula from Croatia (Schmitz, 1924).

9. *Chaetopleurophora erythronota* (Strobl, 1892) – Material examined: [N1.01] Malaise trap: 10–18.V.1997, 5 ♂♂; 28.IV–1.V.1998, 2 ♂♂ • [S1.01] Malaise trap: 4–10.VIII.1998, 2 ♂♂; 10–18.VIII.1998, 1 ♂, 1 ♀; 28.VIII–4.IX.1998, 1 ♀; 25.IX–2.X.1998, 1 ♂ • [N1.05] Malaise trap: 26.VI–3.VII.1998, 2 ♀♀ • between [N1.07] to [N2.01]: 28.VI.1993, 1 ♂. Holarctic species, known from Europe, Asia (Russian Far East) and North America. Other localities in Bulgaria: South Black Sea Coast (Beschovski & Langourov, 1997), Western Rhodope Mts (Langourov, 2010).

** 10. *Chaetopleurophora spinosior* Schmitz, 1938 – Material examined: [N1.06]: 1.V–1.VI.1998, 1 ♂, tree traps; 1.V–1.VI.1999, 1 ♂, soil traps. European species, known from Middle Europe. New region: Balkan Peninsula – Bulgaria.

** 11. *Chaetopleurophora spinosissima* (Strobl, 1892) – Material examined: [N1.01] Malaise trap: 10–18.V.1997, 1 ♀. Palaearctic species, known from Middle and North Europe and Asia (Russian Far East). New region: Balkan Peninsula – Bulgaria.

12. *Conicera dauci* (Meigen, 1830) – Material examined: [S1.01] Malaise trap: 18–28.VIII.1998, 3 ♂♂ • [N1.05] 1150 m: 21.VII.1992, 1 ♂ • [N1.05] Malaise trap: 19–26.VI.1998, 1 ♂; 26.VI–3.VII.1998, 5 ♂♂. Holarctic species, known from Europe, Macaronesia, Asia (Russian Far East, Japan, China) and North America. For the Balkan Peninsula reported also from Montenegro (Langourov, 2004a). Other localities in Bulgaria: Sofia Plain (Langourov, 2004b).

** 13. *Conicera floricola* Schmitz, 1938 – Material examined: [S1.01] Malaise trap: 11–25.IX.1998, 1 ♂; 25.IX–2.X.1998, 1 ♂ • [E1.02]: 15.IV.2000, 1 ♂, on flowers of *Petasites hybridus ochroleucus* (Boiss. et Huet) Sourek • [E1.03]: 15.IV.2000, 1 ♂ • [N1.05] Malaise trap: 29.V–5.VI.1998, 2 ♂♂; 5–12.VI.1998, 2 ♂♂; 19–26.VI.1998, 7 ♂♂, 2 ♀♀; 26.VI–3.VII.1998, 4 ♂♂. Palaearctic species, known from Europe and Asia (Israel, Russian Far East). New region: Balkan Peninsula – Bulgaria.

** 14. *Conicera schnittmanni* Schmitz, 1926 – Material examined: [N1.05] Malaise trap: 3–8.VII.1998, 1 ♂. Palaearctic; known from Europe and Asia (Russian Far East). New region: Balkan Peninsula – Bulgaria.

* 15. *Conicera similis* (Haliday, 1833) – Material examined: [S1.01] Malaise trap: 4–10.VIII.1998, 25 ♂♂; 10–18.VIII.1998, 21 ♂♂; 18–28.VIII.1998, 26 ♂♂; 28.VIII–4.IX.1998, 3 ♂♂; 4–11.IX.1998, 3 ♂♂;

11–25.IX.1998, 2 ♂♂; 25.IX–2.X.1998, 2 ♂♂. Holarctic species, known from Europe, North Africa (Algeria, Egypt), Asia (Turkey, Israel) and North America. For the Balkan Peninsula reported from Croatia (Pax, 1937; Schmitz, 1938).

** 16. *Conicera tibialis* Schmitz, 1925 – Material examined: [S1.01] Malaise trap: 4–10.VIII.1998, 2 ♂♂; 18–28.VIII.1998, 2 ♂♂ • [N1.05] Malaise trap: 19–26.VI.1998, 1 ♂; 26.VI–3.VII.1998, 1 ♂. Holarctic species, known from Europe, North Africa (Egypt), Macaronesia, Asia (Israel, Iran, Tajikistan, Russian Far East) and North America. New region: Balkan Peninsula – Bulgaria.

* 17. *Diplonevra amphichaeta* (Schmitz, 1949) – Material examined: [E1.04] 1000 m, leg. V. Beschovski: 18.VI.1972, 1 ♂. European species, known from Austria and Slovenia (Schmitz, 1953: “Krain: Loitsch” = Logatec). In Beschovski & Langourov, 1997 wrongly determined as *Diplonevra lophochaeta* (Schmitz, 1927).

18. *Diplonevra crassicornis* (Meigen, 1830) – Material examined: [N1.05] Malaise trap: 5–12.VI.1998, 3 ♂♂; 26.VI–3.VII.1998, 3 ♂♂. European species. For the Balkan Peninsula reported from Bosnia-Herzegovina (Strobl, 1898) and Croatia (Langhoffer, 1919). Other localities in Bulgaria: Sofia Plain (Langourov, 2004b).

19. *Diplonevra florescens* (Turton, 1801) – Material examined: [N1.01] Malaise trap: 10–18.V.1997, 5 ♂♂ • [S1.01] Malaise trap: 18–28.VIII.1998, 1 ♂; 28.VIII–4.IX.1998, 1 ♂; 900 m, near Bosnek Village, near Popov Izvor Karst spring, MSS traps: 6.VI–2.X.2013, 8 ♂♂; 1120 m, above Bosnek Village, on the road to Chuipetlyovo, scree in mixed wood, MSS traps: 6.VI–2.X.2013, 1 ♂ • [N1.05] Malaise trap: 29.V–5.VI.1998, 1 ♂; 5–12.VI.1998, 1 ♂. Palearctic; known from Europe and Asia (Armenia, Georgia, Turkey, China, Russian Far East). For the Balkan Peninsula reported from Italy (Schmitz, 1928). Other localities in Bulgaria: Sofia Plain (Beschovski & Langourov, 1997), W Rhodope Mts (Langourov, 2010) and southern part of Vitosha Mt (Langourov et al., 2014).

20. *Diplonevra funebris* (Meigen, 1830) – Material examined: [S1.01] Malaise trap: 4–10.VIII.1998, 16 ♂♂, 5 ♀♀; 10–18.VIII.1998, 18 ♂♂, 1 ♀; 18–28.VIII.1998, 32 ♂♂, 1 ♀; 28.VIII–4.IX.1998, 10 ♂♂; 4–11.IX.1998, 6 ♂♂; 11–25.IX.1998, 12 ♂♂; 25.IX–2.X.1998, 2 ♂♂; 2–31.X.1998, 1 ♂, 1 ♀; 954 m, near Bosnek Village, near Akademik Cave, MSS traps: 6.VI–2.X.2013, 2 ♂♂, 4 ♀♀ • above Bosnek Vil-

lage, 1200 m, oak wood, soil traps (leg. G. Tsonev): 30.VII–18.IX.1994, 1 ♂ • [S2.01]: 31.VII–18.VIII.2000, 2 ♂♂; 18.VIII–1.IX.2000, 2 ♂♂ • [N1.06] soil traps: 1.V–1.VI.1998, 1 ♂. Holarctic; known from Europe, North Africa (Algeria, Egypt), Macaronesia, Asia (Israel, Iran, China, Russian Far East) and North America. For the Balkan Peninsula reported from Croatia (Pax, 1937) and Greece (Disney, 1991). Other localities in Bulgaria: Danube Plain, Lozen Mt (Beschovski & Langourov, 1997), Sofia Plain (Langourov, 2004b), Eastern Rhodope Mts (Langourov, 2004c) and southern part of Vitosha Mt (Langourov et al., 2014).

21. *Diplonevra glabra* (Schmitz, 1927) – Material examined: [N1.01] Malaise trap: 10–18.V.1997, 21 ♂♂, 1 ♀; 22–28.IV.1998, 5 ♂♂ • [N1.04]: 30.V.1993, 1 ♂ • [N1.05] Malaise trap: 29.V–5.VI.1998, 11 ♂♂; 5–12.VI.1998, 5 ♂♂; 19–26.VI.1998, 2 ♂♂ • [N1.06] soil traps: 1.VIII–1.IX.1999, 3 ♀♀. European species. Other localities in Bulgaria: Sofia Plain (Langourov, 2004b).

22. *Diplonevra nitidula* (Meigen, 1830) – Material examined: [S1.01] Malaise trap: 4–10.VIII.1998, 16 ♂♂, 4 ♀♀; 10–18.VIII.1998, 6 ♂♂, 3 ♀♀; 18–28.VIII.1998, 17 ♂♂, 5 ♀♀; 28.VIII–4.IX.1998, 3 ♂♂, 1 ♀; 4–11.IX.1998, 2 ♂♂; 11–25.IX.1998, 1 ♂; 25.IX–2.X.1998, 4 ♂♂; 2–31.X.1998, 11 ♂♂ • [N1.05] Malaise trap: 29.V–5.VI.1998, 1 ♂; 5–12.VI.1998, 1 ♂; 19–26.VI.1998, 6 ♂♂; 26.VI–3.VII.1998, 3 ♂♂, 2 ♀♀; 3–8.VII.1998, 1 ♂ • [N1.06] soil traps: 1.VII–1.VIII.1998, 1 ♂; 1.VI–1.VII.1999, 1 ♂. Holarctic species, known from Europe and North America. For the Balkan Peninsula reported from Greece (Schmitz, 1928). Other localities in Bulgaria: Sofia Plain and Ograzhden Mt (Beschovski & Langourov, 1997).

** 23. *Gymnoptera vitripennis* (Meigen, 1830) – Material examined: [S1.01] Malaise trap: 18–28.VIII.1998, 1 ♂ • [N1.06] soil traps: 1.VII–1.VIII.1998, 1 ♂. European species, known from Middle Europe. New region: Balkan Peninsula – Bulgaria.

** 24. *Peromittra carinifrons* (Zetterstedt, 1848) – Material examined: [N1.06] soil traps: 1.VIII–1.IX.1999, 1 ♂. Palearctic species, known from Middle and North Europe, Asia (Mongolia and Russian Far East). New region: Balkan Peninsula – Bulgaria.

** 25. *Peromittra incrassata* (Meigen, 1830) – Material examined: [N1.02] Malaise trap:

24.VIII–1.IX.1999, 1 ♂ • [S1.01] Malaise trap: 18–28.VIII.1998, 1 ♂ • [E1.05]: 1.VIII–1.IX.1999, 4 ♂♂, soil traps; 2 ♂♂, 1 ♀, tree traps. European species. New region: Balkan Peninsula – Bulgaria.

26. *Phora atra* (Meigen, 1804) – Material examined: [N1.01] Malaise trap: 10–18.V.1997, 3 ♂♂ • [S1.01] Malaise trap: 10–18.VIII.1998, 2 ♂♂; 18–28.VIII.1998, 3 ♂♂; 28.VIII–4.IX.1998, 1 ♂; 11–25.IX.1998, 1 ♂; 17–30.IV.1999, 1 ♂ • [W1.01] tree traps: 8–14.VII.1998, 2 ♂♂. Holarctic species, known from Europe, North Africa (Algeria), Macaronesia, Asia (Israel) and North America. For the Balkan Peninsula reported from Croatia (Langhoffer, 1919) and North Macedonia (Langourov, 1999). Other localities in Bulgaria: Sofia Plain (Langourov, 2004b) and Eastern Rhodope Mts (Langourov, 2004c).

** 27. *Phora dubia* (Zetterstedt, 1848) – Material examined: [N1.01] Malaise trap: 10–18.V.1997, 1 ♂ • [E1.05]: 1.V–1.VI.1998, 1 ♂, 23 ♀♀, tree traps; 1 ♂, 5 ♀♀, soil traps; 1.VII–1.VIII.1998, 1 ♀, tree traps; 1.XI.1998–1.V.1999, 9 ♀♀, tree traps; 1.V–1.VI.1999, 11 ♀♀, tree traps; 1 ♂, soil traps • [N1.06] soil traps: 1.V–1.VI.1998, 1 ♀; 1.V–1.VI.1999, 1 ♀ • 1500 m, E of Septemvri Chalet, beech wood, tree traps (leg. T. Ljubomirov): 3–10.VII.1998, 1 ♀ • 1535–1850 m, between Fonfon Chalet to Konyarnika Place, spruce wood: 26.V.1996, 1 ♂ • [E2.01]: 30.V.1993, 1 ♀; 21.V.1997, 1 ♂, 1 ♀, in copula; 1.V–1.VI.1998, 1 ♂, 3 ♀♀, tree traps; 1.VIII–1.IX.1998, 1 ♂, soil traps; 8.V.1999, 1 ♂; 1.V–1.VI.1999, 1 ♂, 5 ♀♀, tree traps • between [E2.01] to [E2.02]: 30.V.1993, 2 ♂♂, 1 ♀ • between [E2.02] to [E2.03]: 30.V.1993, 1 ♂, 2 ♀♀; 21.V.1997, 1 ♂, 1 ♀, in copula • [N2.02]: 30.V.1993, 2 ♂♂ • [W2.01]: 2.VI.1996, 1 ♂ • 1660–1820 m, between Ostritsa to Edelvais Chalet, spruce wood: 2.VI.1996, 1 ♂ • [E2.03]: 11.VI.1999, 1 ♂, 1 ♀ • [W3.01]: 2.VI.1996, 1 ♂ • [E3.02]: 1.V–1.VI.1999, 3 ♂♂, tree traps; 1 ♂, 2 ♀♀, soil traps; 1.VII–1.VIII.1999, 1 ♀, soil traps • 2100 m, near Golyam Rezen Peak, subalpine zone (leg. E. Manasieva): 4.VI.1995, 1 ♂. Palaearctic species, known from Europe and Asia (Japan). New region: Balkan Peninsula – Bulgaria.

28. *Phora edentata* Schmitz, 1920 – Material examined: [S1.01] Malaise trap: 4–10.VIII.1998, 1 ♂; 10–18.VIII.1998, 1 ♂; 18–28.VIII.1998, 3 ♂♂; 11–25.IX.1998, 2 ♂♂. Palaearctic species, known from Europe and Asia (Russian Far East, Japan, China). For the Balkan Peninsula reported from Croatia (Schmitz, 1955). Other localities in Bulgaria: Sofia

Plain (Langourov, 2004b) and Eastern Rhodope Mts (Langourov, 2004c).

29. *Phora hamata* Schmitz, 1927 – Material examined: [N1.01] Malaise trap: 10–18.V.1997, 3 ♂♂; 12–17.V.1998, 1 ♂ • between [E1.05] to [E1.06]: 27.VIII.1992, 1 ♂. European species, known from Middle Europe. Other localities in Bulgaria: Eastern Rhodope Mts (Langourov, 2004c).

30. *Phora holosericea* Schmitz, 1920 – Material examined: [S1.01] Malaise trap: 10–18.VIII.1998, 1 ♂ • [N1.05] Malaise trap: 3–8.VII.1998, 1 ♂. Holarctic species, known from Europe, Asia (Israel, Iran, Kyrgyzstan, Mongolia, China, South Korea, Japan, Russian Far East) and North America. For the Balkan Peninsula reported from Greece (Disney, 1991) and North Macedonia (Langourov, 1999). Other localities in Bulgaria: Sofia Plain (Langourov, 2004b) and Western Rhodope Mts (Langourov, 2010).

** 31. *Phora horrida* Schmitz, 1920 – Material examined: [E3.02], tree traps: 1.V–1.VI.1999, 1 ♂, 1 ♀. European high mountain species, known from Middle Europe (Alps, Tatra Mts and Carpathian Mts). New region: Balkan Peninsula – Bulgaria.

32. *Phora penicillata* Schmitz, 1920 – Material examined: [N1.07]: 31.V.1998, 1 ♂ • between [E2.01] to [E2.03]: 20.VIII.1992, 1 ♂ • [E3.02], soil traps: 1.VII–1.VIII.1999, 1 ♂, 1 ♀ • [S4.01]: 6.VI–5.VII.1999, 1 ♂. European species. Other localities in Bulgaria: W Rhodope Mts (Langourov, 2010).

* 33. *Phora pubipes* Schmitz, 1920 – Material examined: [E1.04]: 27.VIII.1992, 1 ♂ • [E1.05]: 1.VIII–1.IX.1998, 1 ♂, 1 ♀, tree traps; 1.VIII–1.IX.1999, 1 ♂, 1 ♀, tree traps; 1 ♂, 3 ♀♀, soil traps • 1500 m, E of Septemvri Chalet, beech wood, tree traps: 3–10.VII.1998, 1 ♂ • between [E2.01] to [E2.03]: 20.VIII.1992, 2 ♂ • [E2.01]: 1.VIII–1.IX.1998, 2 ♂♂, soil traps; 1.VII–1.VIII.1999, 1 ♂, tree traps; 1.VIII–1.IX.1999, 1 ♂, 1 ♀, tree traps; 1 ♂, soil traps. Palaearctic-Oriental species, known from Europe, Asia (Mongolia, Japan) and Oriental Region. For the Balkan Peninsula reported from Bosnia-Herzegovina (Strobl, 1898 as *Trineura aterrma*).

34. *Phora stictica* Meigen, 1830 – Material examined: 1260–1360 m, near Esperanto (Zeleni Patrule) Chalet, mixed wood: 3.IX.1992, 1 ♂ • [E1.05], tree traps: 1.VIII–1.IX.1999, 1 ♂ • between [E1.05] to [E1.06]: 27.VIII.1992, 1 ♂ • [E1.06]: 20.VIII.1992, 1 ♂ • between [E1.06] to [E2.01]: 3.IX.1992, 1 ♂ • [N1.07]: 20.VIII.1992, 1 ♂ • [E2.01]: 1.VIII–1.IX.1998, 4 ♂♂, soil traps; 1.VII–1.VIII.1999,

2 ♂♂, 1 ♀, tree traps; 1 ♂, soil traps; 1.VIII–1.IX.1999, 2 ♂♂, 6 ♀♀, tree traps; 4 ♂♂, soil traps • between [E2.01] to [E2.02]: 27.VIII.1992, 1 ♂; 3.IX.1992, 1 ♂ • [N2.01]: 21.VII.1992, 1 ♂, on *Rubus* sp. leaf • [N2.03]: 20.VII.1992, 1 ♂ • 1840 m, near Aleko Chalet, spruce wood (leg. V. Beschovski): 10.VIII.1984, 1 ♂ • [E3.02], tree traps: 1.VIII–1.IX.1999, 2 ♂♂, 2 ♀♀ • [E3.04]: 5.VIII.1999, 7 ♂♂, 1 ♀, on racemes of *A. sylvestris* L. Holarctic-Neotropical; known from Europe, North America and South America (withouth southernmost part). Reported from Croatia (Schmitz, 1955) and North Macedonia (Langourov, 1999). Other localities in Bulgaria: W Rhodope Mts (Langourov, 2010).

35. *Phora tincta* Schmitz, 1920 – Material examined: [N1.01] Malaise trap: 22–28.IV.1998, 1 ♂ • [N1.05] 1150 m: 21.VII.1992, 2 ♂♂ • [E1.05]: 1.V–1.VI.1999, 1 ♂, tree traps; 2 ♂♂, soil traps • between [E1.05] to [E1.06]: 20.VIII.1992, 1 ♂ • [N1.06]: 20.VIII.1992, 2 ♂♂; 1.VI–1.VII.1999, 1 ♂, soil traps • [E1.06]: 11.VI.1999, 2 ♂♂, on *Rubus idaeus* leaves • [E2.01]: 1.VII–1.VIII.1998, 2 ♂♂, tree traps; 1.VIII–1.IX.1998, 3 ♂♂, soil traps; 1.VII–1.VIII.1999, 5 ♂♂, tree traps; 2 ♂♂, 1 ♀, soil traps • between [E2.01] to [E2.02]: 28.VI.1993, 4 ♂♂ • [N2.01]: 21.VII.1992, 1 ♂, on flowers of *Anthriscus nitida* (Wahlenb.) Garcke • between [E2.02] to [E2.03]: 28.VI.1993, 2 ♂♂ • [E2.02]: 11.VI.1999, 1 ♂, 1 ♀, in copula – on *Rubus idaeus* leaf. Palaearctic species, known from Europe and Asia (Israel, West Siberia, Tajikistan). For the Balkan Peninsula reported from Croatia (Schmitz, 1924) Slovenia (Schmitz, 1928) and Montenegro (Langourov, 2004a). Other localities in Bulgaria: Western Rhodope Mts (Langourov, 2010).

36. *Spiniphora bergenstammi* (Mik, 1864) – Material examined: [N1.02] Malaise trap: 1–18.IX.1999, 1 ♂ • [S1.01] Malaise trap: 4–10.VIII.1998, 2 ♂♂; 10–18.VIII.1998, 4 ♂♂; 28.VIII–4.IX.1998, 3 ♂♂; 4–11.IX.1998, 1 ♂. Cosmopolitan species. For the Balkan Peninsula reported from Italy, Croatia, Greece (Schmitz, 1928) and North Macedonia (Langourov, 1999). Other localities in Bulgaria: Sofia Plain (Beschovski & Langourov, 1997).

* 37. *Spiniphora dorsalis* (Becker, 1901) – Material examined: [N1.06], soil traps: 1.IX–1.X.1998, 2 ♂♂; 1.X–1.XI.1998, 1 ♂; 1.IX–1.X.1999, 1 ♂; 1.X–1.XI.1999, 1 ♂ • [N3.02]: 6.VIII–8.IX.1999, 1 ♂. European species. For the Balkan Peninsula reported from Croatia (Becker, 1901) and North Macedonia (Langourov, 1999).

* 38. *Spiniphora jugorum* (Schmitz, 1924) – Material examined: [E2.01]: 1.VII–1.VIII.1999, 1 ♂, tree traps • [E3.02], tree traps: 1.VIII–1.IX.1998, 1 ♂; 1.V–1.VI.1999, 1 ♂; 1.VII–1.VIII.1999, 2 ♂♂; 1.VIII–1.IX.1999, 1 ♂ • [E3.04]: 5.VIII.1999, 1 ♀, on racemes of *Angelica sylvestris* L. • [E3.04] soil traps: 1.VI–1.VII.1999, 3 ♂♂; 1.XI.1999–1.V.2000, 1 ♂ • [S4.02] soil traps: 6.VI–3.VII.1999, 2 ♂♂. Euro-Caucasian species, known from the Alps, Tatra Mts, Durmitor Mt and Caucasus. For the Balkan Peninsula reported from Montenegro (Schmitz, 1928).

39. *Spiniphora maculata* (Meigen, 1830) – Material examined: [N1.01] Malaise trap: 22–28.IV.1998, 1 ♂ • [S1.01] Malaise trap: 3–17.IV.1999, 4 ♂♂; 17–30.IV.1999, 2 ♂♂ • [N1.06], tree traps: 15.IV–1.V.1999, 1 ♂ • [E3.04] soil traps: 1.VIII–1.IX.1998, 1 ♂; 15.V–1.VI.1999, 1 ♂. European; for the Balkan Peninsula reported from Croatia (Strobl, 1902) and Italy (Schmitz, 1928). In Bulgaria: E Rhodope Mts (Langourov, 2004c).

40. *Triphleba antricola* (Schmitz, 1918) – Material examined: [S1.01] Malaise trap: 11–25.IX.1998, 1 ♀; 17–30.IV.1999, 2 ♂♂; 900 m, near Bosnek Village, near Popov Izvor Karst spring, MSS traps: 6.VI–2.X.2013, 3 ♀♀; 910 m, near Bosnek Village, Popov Izvor Cave, soil traps: 2.X–2.XI.2013, 8 ♂♂, 31 ♀♀; 1006 m, near Bosnek Village, near Duhlata Cave, MSS traps: 6.VI–2.X.2013, 1 ♂; 1118 m, near Bosnek Village, Zhivata Voda Cave, soil traps: 13.VIII–15.XI.2013, 20 ♂♂, 158 ♀♀ • 847 m, above Boyana, Boyanski Kamak place, microcave, MSS trap: 30.IV–3.VI.2006, 8 ♀♀; [N1.06]: 1.IX–1.X.1998, 1 ♂, soil traps; 4.XI.1998, 1 ♀, among fallen leaves. South-european species, widespread in the country. For the Balkan Peninsula also known from Bosnia and Herzegovina (Bezzi, 1911; Schmitz, 1919), Italy, Slovenia, Croatia, Serbia (Schmitz, 1919), Greece and Romania (Langourov, 2001). For the mountain reported also from Duhlata Cave (Hazelton, 1970).

41. *Triphleba autumnalis* (Becker, 1901) – Material examined: [E1.05]: 17.X.1992, 1 ♂; 1.XI.1998–1.V.1999, 1 ♂, soil traps; 1.X–1.XI.1999, 2 ♂♂, soil traps; 1.XI.1999–1.IV.2000, 1 ♂, soil traps • [N1.06]: 1.IX–1.X.1998, 2 ♂♂, soil traps; 4.XI.1998, 1 ♂, among fallen leaves; 1.XI.1998–15.IV.1999, 1 ♀, tree traps; 1 ♂, soil traps; 1.X–1.XI.1999, 1 ♂, 2 ♀♀, soil traps; 1.XI.1999–1.IV.2000, 4 ♂♂, 1 ♀, soil traps • [N1.06]: 2.X.1999, 1 ♀ • [E2.01], soil traps: 1.X–1.XI.1999, 1 ♂. European species. Other localities in Bulgaria: Eastern Rhodope Mts (Langourov, 2004c).

42. *Triphleba bicornuta* (Strobl, 1910) – Material examined: [S1.01] Malaise trap: 25.IX–2.X.1998, 1 ♂, 1 ♀; 2–31.X.1998, 8 ♂♂ • between [E1.05] to [E1.06]: 27.VIII.1992, 1 ♀ • [N1.06]: 1.X–1.XI.1998, 1 ♂, 1 ♀, tree traps; 2 ♂♂, 1 ♀, soil traps • [E2.01]: 2.X.1998, 1 ♂; 1.IX–1.X.1999, 1 ♂, soil traps • between [E2.01] to [E2.02]: 3.IX.1992, 1 ♂ • [E2.02]: 17.X.1992, 1 ♂ • [E3.02], soil traps: 1.VIII–1.IX.1998, 1 ♂; 1.IX–1.X.1998, 1 ♂; 1.IX–1.X.1999, 2 ♂♂ • [W3.02] soil traps: 6.IX–4.X.1999, 2 ♂♂ • [E3.04] soil traps: 1.VIII–1.IX.1998, 2 ♂♂; 1.IX–1.X.1998, 3 ♂♂; 1.VIII–1.IX.1999, 2 ♂♂, 1 ♀; 1.IX–1.X.1999, 3 ♂♂, 1 ♀ • [S4.03]: 6.VIII–8.IX.1999, 1 ♀. European species, known from North Europe and the mountains of Middle Europe. Other localities in Bulgaria: Rila Mts (Beschovski & Langourov, 1997).

** 43. *Triphleba citreiformis* (Becker, 1901) – Material examined: [N1.05] Malaise trap: 5–12.VI.1998, 1 ♀. European species. New region: Balkan Peninsula – Bulgaria.

44. *Triphleba distinguenda* (Strobl, 1892) – Material examined: [N1.01] Malaise trap: 10–18.V.1997, 46 ♂♂, 2 ♀♀; 22–28.IV.1998, 1 ♂; 28.IV–1.V.1998, 3 ♂♂ • [S1.01] Malaise trap: 4–10.VIII.1998, 3 ♂♂, 2 ♀♀; 10–18.VIII.1998, 3 ♂♂; 18–28.VIII.1998, 3 ♂♂, 1 ♀; 28.VIII–4.IX.1998, 1 ♀; 11–25.IX.1998, 5 ♂♂; 25.IX–2.X.1998, 8 ♂♂; 2–31.X.1998, 3 ♂♂; 900 m, near Bosnek Village, near Popov Izvor Karst spring, MSS traps: 6.VI–2.X.2013, 4 ♂♂, 9 ♀♀ • [N1.03]: 28.VI.1993, 1 ♂ • 1260–1360 m, near Esperanto Chalet, mixed wood: 27.VIII.1992, 1 ♀ • [N1.05] Malaise trap: 29.V–5.VI.1998, 1 ♂; 19–26.VI.1998, 2 ♂♂ • [N1.06]: 3.IX.1992, 1 ♀; 1.VIII–1.IX.1998, 1 ♀, soil traps; 1.V–1.VI.1999, 1 ♀, soil traps; 1.IX–1.X.1999, 1 ♀, soil traps • between [N1.06] to [N1.07]: 27.VIII.1992, 1 ♀ • [E1.06]: 20.VIII.1992, 1 ♂ • between [N1.07] to [N2.01]: 28.VI.1993, 1 ♂. Palearctic species, known from Europe and Asia (Russian Far East). For the Balkan Peninsula also known from Montenegro (Langourov, 2004a). Other localities in Bulgaria: Sofia Plain and Vitosha Mountain (Beschovski & Langourov, 1997; Langourov et al., 2014).

45. *Triphleba dudai* (Schmitz, 1918) – Material examined: between [N1.03] to [N1.04]: 30.V.1993, 1 ♂ • 1260–1360 m, near Esperanto Chalet, mixed wood: 27.VIII.1992, 1 ♀ • [N1.05] Malaise trap: 26.VI–3.VII.1998, 1 ♂. European species. Published for the mountain by Beschovski & Langourov (1997).

46. *Triphleba gracilis* (Wood, 1907) – Material examined: [N1.01] Malaise trap: 10–18.V.1997, 1 ♂ •

[E2.01], tree traps: 1.IX–1.X.1998, 1 ♀; 1.VIII–1.IX.1999, 1 ♂, 2 ♀♀ • between [E2.01] to [E2.02]: 27.VIII.1992, 1 ♂ • [E2.02]: 3.IX.1992, 1 ♀ • between [E2.02] to [E2.03]: 17.X.1992, 1 ♀ • [E2.03]: 3.IX.1992, 1 ♂. European species. Published for the mountain by Beschovski & Langourov (1997).

47. *Triphleba hyalinata* (Meigen, 1830) – Material examined: [N1.02]: 27.X.1999, 1 ♀ • [E1.05]: 1.IX–1.X.1998, 1 ♀, tree traps; 1.X–1.XI.1998, 1 ♀, tree traps; 1.IX–1.X.1999, 2 ♀♀, tree traps; 1.X–1.XI.1999, 1 ♀, tree traps; 1 ♀, soil traps; 964 m, near Bosnek Village, near Duhlata Cave, MSS trap: 18.IV–16.VI.2007. European species. For the Balkan Peninsula also known from Italy (Funk & Graffe, 1895). Other localities in Bulgaria: Central Stara Planina Mts, Enina Village; Sofia Plain, Sofia and Vitosha Mt (Langourov, 2001; Langourov et al., 2014); Eastern Rhodope Mts (Langourov, 2004c).

** 48. *Triphleba hypopygialis* (Schmitz, 1918) – Material examined: [E2.01]: 1.IX–1.X.1998, 1 ♂, tree traps; 1.VII–1.VIII.1999, 1 ♂, 1 ♀, tree traps; 1.VIII–1.IX.1999, 1 ♀, soil traps • [E3.02], soil traps: 1.VIII–1.IX.1999, 1 ♂. European species, known till now from Austria, Germany and France. New region: Balkan Peninsula – Bulgaria.

49. *Triphleba inaequalis* Schmitz, 1943 – Material examined: [E1.04]: 17.X.1992, 1 ♂ • [E1.05], tree traps: 1.IX–1.X.1998, 1 ♂; 1.XI.1998–1.V.1999, 1 ♂; 1.IX–1.X.1999, 1 ♂; 900 m, near Bosnek Village, near Popov Izvor Karst spring, MSS traps: 2.X–2.XI.2013, 4 ♂♂. European species. Reported also for the southern part of Vitosha Mt (Langourov et al., 2014).

50. *Triphleba intermedia* (Malloch, 1908) – Material examined: [S1.01] Malaise trap: 3–17.IV.1999, 3 ♂♂ • 1100 m, above Zhelezmitsa Village, mixed wood (leg. V. Beschovski): 18.V.1982, 5 ♂♂, 1 ♀ • [E1.03]: 15.IV.2000, 1 ♂ • 1830 m, Bistrishko Branishte Reserve, near Fizkulturnik Chalet, subalpine zone (leg. V. Beschovski): 18.V.1982, 25 ♂♂, 1 ♀ • [E3.02]: 27.IV.2000, 1 ♀ • [E3.02], tree traps: 1.V–1.VI.1999, 1 ♂, 1 ♀ • [N3.03] soil traps: 29.V–4.VII.1999, 1 ♀ • [W3.04] soil traps: 5.VI–3.VII.1999, 1 ♀ • [E3.04], on snow: 27.IV.2000, 1 ♀ • [E3.04] soil traps: 15.V–1.VI.1999, 8 ♂♂, 2 ♀♀; 1.VI–1.VII.1999, 1 ♂ • [S4.03]: 5.VI–5.VII.1999, 1 ♂. European species. Other localities in Bulgaria: Eastern Rhodope Mts (Langourov, 2004b) and Western Rhodope Mts (Langourov, 2010).

** 51. *Triphleba longifurcata* (Schmitz, 1922) – Material examined: [N1.06], soil traps:

1.VIII–1.IX.1998, 1 ♀. European species, known till now only from the type-locality in Hungary. New region: Balkan Peninsula – Bulgaria.

* 52. *Triphleba lugubris* (Meigen, 1830) – Material examined: [S1.01] Malaise trap: 25.IX–2.X.1998, 1 ♂ • [E1.05] soil traps: 1.VIII–1.IX.1998, 1 ♂. Holarctic-Oriental; known from Europe, North America and Oriental Region. On the Balkan Peninsula – Croatia (Pax, 1937 as *Diploneura* [sic!] *lugubris* (Meigen)).

53. *Triphleba nudipalpis* (Becker, 1901) – Material examined: [N1.01] Malaise trap: 10–18.V.1997, 21 ♂♂, 2 ♀♀ • [S1.01] Malaise trap: 4–10.VIII.1998, 29 ♂♂, 1 ♀; 10–18.VIII.1998, 22 ♂♂; 18–28.VIII.1998, 13 ♂♂; 28.VIII–4.IX.1998, 3 ♂♂; 4–11.IX.1998, 1 ♂, 1 ♀; 11–25.IX.1998, 5 ♂♂; 25.IX–2.X.1998, 2 ♂♂; 2–31.X.1998, 3 ♂♂, 1 ♀. European species. Other localities in Bulgaria: Kresna Gorge (Langourov & Sakalian, 2001).

54. *Triphleba opaca* (Meigen, 1830) – Material examined: [S1.01] Malaise trap: 3–17.IV.1999, 1 ♀ • [E1.05]: 1.XI.1998–1.V.1999, 1 ♀, soil traps; 1.XI.1999–1.IV.2000, 1 ♂, tree traps • [N1.06]: 1.XI.1998–15.IV.1999, 1 ♂, tree traps; 15.IV–1.V.1999, 1 ♂, 1 ♀, tree traps; 1 ♀, soil traps; 1.XI.1999–1.IV.2000, 2 ♂♂, soil traps • [N1.07]: 19.IV.1993, 1 ♀ • [E2.03]: 30.V.1993, 1 ♂ • [E3.02]: 1.V–1.VI.1998, 1 ♀, soil traps; 1.X.1998–1.V.1999, 1 ♂, tree traps; 1 ♂, soil traps; 1.V–1.VI.1999, 17 ♂♂, tree traps; 5 ♂♂, soil traps; 1.XI.1999–1.V.2000, 1 ♂, soil traps • [W3.02] soil traps: 5.VI–3.VII.1999, 3 ♀♀ • [W3.05] soil traps: 5.VI–3.VII.1999, 2 ♀♀ • [W3.04] soil traps: 5.VI–3.VII.1999, 1 ♀ • [E3.04], on snow: 27.IV.2000, 2 ♂♂ • 2150 m, Suhoto Ezero near Cherni Vruh, subalpine zone, on snow (leg. E. Manasieva): 13.III.1994, 3 ♂♂ • [E3.04] soil traps: 1.VIII–1.IX.1998, 1 ♂; 1.X.1998–15.V.1999, 2 ♂♂; 15.V–1.VI.1999, 9 ♂♂, 1 ♀ • 2191 m, Malak Rezen, subalpine zone: 28.V.1998, 13 ♂♂; 14.V.1999, 1 ♂ on snow • 2280 m, Cherni Vruh, subalpine zone: 26.V.1996, 1 ♂. Palaearctic; known from Europe and Asia (W Siberia and Russian Far East). For the Balkan Peninsula known from Italy (Funk & Graffe, 1895), Albania and former Yugoslavia (Disney, 1991).

** 55. *Triphleba pachyneurella* (Schmitz, 1919) – Material examined: [E2.02]: 28.V.1998, 1 ♂ • [E3.02]: 1.X.1998–1.V.1999, 1 ♂, soil traps; 1.V–1.VI.1999, 2 ♂♂, tree traps • [E3.04] soil traps: 15.V–1.VI.1999, 1 ♂ • 2280 m, Cherni Vruh Peak, subalpine zone (leg. V. Beschovski): 18.V.1982, 1 ♂, on flower of *Crocus veluchensis* Herb. European species, known till now

from Austria, Italy, Slovakia, Sweden and Finland. New region: Balkan Peninsula – Bulgaria.

56. *Triphleba papillata* (Wingate, 1906) – Material examined: [E1.05] soil traps: 1.V–1.VI.1999, 3 ♂♂ • [N1.05] Malaise trap: 29.V–5.VI.1998, 3 ♂♂ • [N1.06]: 1.XI.1998–15.IV.1999, 1 ♂, 1 ♀, tree traps; 1.V–1.VI.1999, 2 ♂♂, 2 ♀♀, soil traps • [E2.02]: 28.V.1998, 1 ♂; 964 m, near Bosnek, near Duhlata Cave, MSS trap: 18.IV–16.VI.2007. European; in Bulgaria: Eastern Rhodope Mts (Langourov, 2004b) and southern parts of Vitosha Mt (Langourov et al., 2014).

57. *Triphleba trinervis* (Becker, 1901) – Material examined: [S2.01]: 8–31.X.2000, 1 ♀ • [E1.05]: 1.X–1.XI.1998, 2 ♂♂, 3 ♀♀, tree traps; 2 ♂♂, 1 ♀, soil traps; 1.XI.1998–1.V.1999, 1 ♂, 1 ♀, tree traps; 13 ♂♂, 6 ♀♀, soil traps; 1.X–1.XI.1999, 4 ♂♂, 3 ♀♀, tree traps; 3 ♂♂, 10 ♀♀, soil traps; 1.XI.1999–1.IV.2000, 1 ♂, 3 ♀♀, tree traps; 12 ♂♂, 12 ♀♀, soil traps • [N1.06]: 1.X–1.XI.1998, 10 ♂♂, 13 ♀♀, tree traps; 7 ♂♂, 17 ♀♀, soil traps; 4.XI.1998, 1 ♂, 2 ♀♀, among fallen leaves; 1.XI.1998–15.IV.1999, 4 ♂♂, 3 ♀♀, tree traps; 45 ♂♂, 32 ♀♀, soil traps; 1.X–1.XI.1999, 2 ♂♂, 3 ♀♀, tree traps; 6 ♂♂, 12 ♀♀, soil traps; 27.X.1999, 3 ♂♂, 3 ♀♀, numerous among fallen leaves; 1.XI.1999–1.IV.2000, 1 ♂, tree traps; 53 ♂♂, 67 ♀♀, one pair in copula, soil traps • [E2.01]: 1.X–1.XI.1998, 1 ♂, tree traps; 1 ♂, 1 ♀, soil traps; 1.XI.1998–1.V.1999, 1 ♀, soil traps; 1.X–1.XI.1999, 1 ♀, tree traps; 1.XI.1999–1.IV.2000, 10 ♂♂, 8 ♀♀, soil traps • 1590 m, near Sredets Chalet, spruce wood: 4.XI.1998, 1 ♀ • [E3.02]: 1.X.1998–1.V.1999, 1 ♂, soil traps; 1.X–1.XI.1999, 1 ♀, tree traps; 1.XI.1999–1.V.2000, 1 ♀, soil traps • [E3.04] soil traps: 1.X.1998–15.V.1999, 2 ♀♀; 1.X–1.XI.1999, 1 ♂; 1.XI.1999–1.V.2000, 1 ♂, 2 ♀♀. Holarctic species. Other localities in Bulgaria: Sofia Plain (Beschovski & Langourov, 1997) and Eastern Rhodope Mts (Langourov, 2004b).

58. *Triphleba tumidula* (Schmitz, 1918) – Material examined: [E1.03]: 15.IV.2000, 1 ♂. European species. Other localities in Bulgaria: Eastern Rhodope Mts (Langourov, 2004b).

** 59. *Triphleba vitrea* (Wood, 1906) – Material examined: [E3.03] soil traps: 5.X–1.XI.1999, 1 ♀. European species, known till now from Austria, Great Britain, Slovakia and Netherlands. New region: Balkan Peninsula – Bulgaria.

** 60. *Triphleba withersi* Disney, 1992 – Material examined: [N1.01] Malaise trap: 10–18.V.1997, 4 ♂♂,

1 ♀ • [S1.01] Malaise trap: 4–10.VIII.1998, 7 ♂♂; 18–28.VIII.1998, 8 ♂♂; 28.VIII–4.IX.1998, 2 ♂♂; 11–25.IX.1998, 3 ♂♂. Mediterranean species, known till now only from the type-locality in France. New region: Balkan Peninsula – Bulgaria.

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** 61. *Megaselia abernethae* Disney, 1988 – Material examined: [N1.06], tree traps: 1.VI–1.VII.1999, 1 ♂. European species, known till now only from the type-locality in Scotland (Great Britain). New region: Balkan Peninsula – Bulgaria.

62. *Megaselia aculeata* (Schmitz, 1919) – Material examined: [S1.01] Malaise trap: 4–10.VIII.1998, 8 ♂♂; 10–18.VIII.1998, 1 ♂; 18–28.VIII.1998, 5 ♂♂; 28.VIII–4.IX.1998, 1 ♂ • [E2.01], soil traps: 1.IX–1.X.1999, 1 ♂ • [E3.01] soil traps: 7.VIII–6.IX.1999, 9 ♂♂, 2 ♀♀ • [N3.02]: 12.VI–4.VII.1999, 5 ♂♂ • [E3.02]: 1.VI–1.VII.1999, 2 ♂♂, soil traps; 1.VII–1.VIII.1999, 2 ♂♂, tree traps; 1.VIII–1.IX.1999, 1 ♂, 3 ♀♀, tree traps; 1.IX–1.X.1999, 1 ♂, tree traps; 1 ♂, soil traps • [E3.04]: 5.VIII.1999, 2 ♂♂, on racemes of *Angelica sylvestris* L. • [W3.04] soil traps: 3.VII–7.VIII.1999, 4 ♂♂, 1 ♀ • [W3.06] soil traps: 3.VII–6.VIII.1999, 2 ♂♂, 1 ♀; 7.VIII–6.IX.1999, 2 ♂♂ • [E3.04] soil traps: 1.VII–1.VIII.1999, 1 ♂, 1 ♀. Westpalaearctic species, known from Europe and Asia (Iran). Other localities in Bulgaria: Western Rhodope Mts (Langourov, 2010).

63. *Megaselia aequalis* (Wood, 1909) – Material examined: [E1.01]: 15.IV.2000, 1 ♀ • [N1.04]: 30.V.1993, 1 ♂ • 1260–1360 m, near Esperanto Chalet, mixed wood: 30.V.1993, 1 ♂ • [E1.05], tree traps: 1.V–1.VI.1999, 1 ♀ • [N1.05] Malaise trap: 29.V–5.VI.1998, 1 ♂; 5–12.VI.1998, 5 ♂♂ • [N1.06]: 1.V–1.VI.1998, 1 ♂, soil traps; 1 ♀, tree traps; 1.V–1.VI.1999, 1 ♂, 1 ♀, tree traps; 1 ♀, soil traps; 1.VI–1.VII.1999, 1 ♂, 2 ♀♀, soil traps • 1500 m, E of Septemvri Chalet, beech wood, tree traps: 3–10.VII.1998, 1 ♀ • [E2.01]: 1.IX–1.X.1998, 1 ♂, soil traps; 2.X.1998, 1 ♀ • [N2.03]: 20.VIII.1992, 1 ♂, 1 ♀, in copula • [E3.02]: 1.V–1.VI.1999, 1 ♂, tree traps; 1.VII–1.VIII.1999, 1 ♂, soil traps; 1.VIII–1.IX.1999, 3 ♂♂, 2 ♀♀, tree traps; 1 ♂, 1 ♀, soil traps • 2150 m, near Malak Rezen, subalpine zone: 28.V.1998, 1 ♀. Holarctic; known from Europe, Asia (Israel, Russian Far East) and North America. For the Balkan Peninsula also known from Croatia, Slovenia (Schmitz, 1924, 1928e), North Macedonia (Coe, 1956; Langourov,

1999) and Montenegro (Langourov, 2004a). Other localities in Bulgaria: W Rhodope Mts (Langourov, 2010).

** 64. *Megaselia affinis* (Wood, 1909) – Material examined: [S1.01] Malaise trap: 28.VIII–4.IX.1998, 3 ♂♂; 2–31.X.1998, 1 ♂. European species. New region: Balkan Peninsula – Bulgaria.

** 65. *Megaselia albicans* (Wood, 1908) – Material examined: [N1.06]: 1.XI.1998–15.IV.1999, 1 ♂, 1 ♀, tree traps; 15.IV–1.V.1999, 3 ♂♂, 1 ♀, tree traps; 1 ♂, soil traps. European species, known from Middle Europe and Sweden. New region: Balkan Peninsula – Bulgaria.

66. *Megaselia albicaudata* (Wood, 1910) – Material examined: [S1.01] Malaise trap: 17–30.IV.1999, 1 ♂ • [S2.01]: 31.VII–18.VIII.2000, 1 ♂. Holarctic species, known from Europe, Macaronesia (Canary Is), Asia (Israel, Iran, Yemen, China) and North America. For the Balkan Peninsula also known from Montenegro (Langourov, 2004a). Other localities in Bulgaria: Western Rhodope Mts (Langourov, 2010).

** 67. *Megaselia albiclava* Schmitz, 1926 – Material examined: [N1.05] Malaise trap: 29.V–5.VI.1998, 1 ♂ • [N1.06] soil traps: 1.VII–1.VIII.1999, 1 ♂. European species, known till now from Middle and North Europe. New region: Balkan Peninsula – Bulgaria.

68. *Megaselia albocingulata* (Strobl, 1906) – Material examined: [S1.01] Malaise trap: 18–28.VIII.1998, 2 ♂♂; 978 m, near Bosnek Village, near Pepelyankata Cave: 2.X–2.XI.2013, 1 ♂, 4 ♀♀; 1006 m, near Bosnek Village, near Duhlata Cave, MSS traps: 6.VI–2.X.2013, 1 ♂, 4 ♀♀. Mediterranean species; also known from Iran. For the Balkan Peninsula known from Croatia (Schmitz, 1924 as *Aphiochaeta languescens* (Schmitz, 1924)) and Greece (Disney, 1991). Published for the mountain by Langourov et al. (2014).

** 69. *Megaselia alticolella* (Wood, 1909) – Material examined: [W3.05] soil traps: 7.VIII–6.IX.1999, 1 ♂. European species. New region: Balkan Peninsula – Bulgaria.

70. *Megaselia altifrons* (Wood, 1909) – Material examined: [S1.01] Malaise trap: 4–10.VIII.1998, 1 ♂; 28.VIII–4.IX.1998, 1 ♂ • [E2.01], soil traps: 1.VIII–1.IX.1998, 1 ♂. Westpalaearctic species, known from Europe and Asia (Iran). For the Balkan Peninsula is also known from Slovenia (Schmitz, 1928). Other localities in Bulgaria: Sofia Plain (Beschovski & Langourov, 1997; Langourov, 2004b) and Western Rhodope Mts (Langourov, 2010).

71. *Megaselia angusta* (Wood, 1909) – Material examined: [E1.02]: 15.IV.2000, 1 ♂, on flowers of *Petasites hybridus ochroleucus* (Boiss. et Huet) Sourek; 954 m, near Bosnek Village, near Akademik Cave, MSS traps: 6.VI–2.XI.2013, 1 ♂; 1120 m, above Bosnek, on the road to Chuipetlyovo, scree in mixed wood, MSS traps: 2.X–2.XI.2013, 2 ♂♂. Westpalaeartic species, known from Europe, Macaronesia and Asia (Israel). For the Balkan Peninsula is known also from Slovenia (Schmitz, 1928), Croatia (Coe, 1956) and Montenegro (Langourov, 2004a). In Bulgaria also known from W Rhodope Mts (Langourov, 2010) and other parts of Vitosha Mt (Langourov et al., 2014).

** 72. *Megaselia aquilonia* Schmitz, 1958 – Material examined: [E3.02], soil traps: 1.V–1.VI.1999, 1 ♂; 1.VI–1.VII.1999, 1 ♂. European species, known till now from Great Britain, Poland, Norway and Sweden. New region: Balkan Peninsula – Bulgaria.

73. *Megaselia basispinata* (Lundbeck, 1920) – Material examined: [S2.01]: 31.VII–18.VIII.2000, 1 ♂ • [N1.06]: 1.VIII–1.IX.1998, 1 ♂, tree traps; 1.VI–1.VII.1999, 1 ♂, soil traps • [E3.02], tree traps: 1.VII–1.VIII.1998, 1 ♂, 1 ♀. Holarctic-Neotropical species. For the Balkan Peninsula is also known from Slovenia (Schmitz, 1928). Other localities in Bulgaria: Eastern Rhodope Mts (Langourov, 2004b) and Sofia Plain (Langourov, 2005).

** 74. *Megaselia beckeri* (Wood, 1909) – Material examined: [N1.06]: 27.VIII.1992, 1 ♂ • between [E2.01] to [E2.02]: 3.IX.1992, 1 ♂. Holarctic species, known from Middle and North Europe and North America. New region: Balkan Peninsula – Bulgaria.

75. *Megaselia berndseni* (Schmitz, 1919) – Material examined: [E1.05], tree traps: 1.VII–1.VIII.1999, 1 ♂ • [N1.06] soil traps: 1.VIII–1.IX.1998, 1 ♀; 1.V–1.VI.1999, 1 ♂ • [E2.01], soil traps: 1.VII–1.VIII.1998, 1 ♂ • 1830 m, Aleko Chalet, on window (leg. S. Lazarov): 2.V.1999, 1 ♂ • [E3.02], tree traps: 1.VIII–1.IX.1999, 1 ♀. Holarctic species, known for the Balkan Peninsula from Greece (Schmitz, 1924) and North Macedonia [Coe, 1956 as *Megaselia pygmaeoides* (Lundbeck)]. Other localities in Bulgaria: Eastern Rhodope Mts (Langourov, 2004b).

** 76. *Megaselia bovista* (Gimmerthal, 1848) – Material examined: [E3.02], tree traps: 1.VI–1.VII.1999, 1 ♂. Westpalaeartic species, known from Europe and Asia (Israel and Iran). New region: Balkan Peninsula – Bulgaria.

77. *Megaselia brevicostalis* (Wood, 1910) – Material examined: [E2.01], soil traps: 1.IX–1.X.1999, 1 ♂ •

[E3.02], soil traps: 1.V–1.VI.1999, 1 ♂ • [E3.04] soil traps: 1.VII–1.VIII.1999, 1 ♂. Holarctic-Neotropical species. For the Balkan Peninsula also known from Slovenia (Schmitz, 1928), North Macedonia (Coe, 1956) and Montenegro (Langourov, 2004a). Other localities in Bulgaria: Western Stara Planina Mts (Schmitz, 1953), Eastern Rhodope Mountains (Langourov, 2004b) and Western Rhodope Mts (Langourov, 2010).

78. *Megaselia brevior* (Schmitz, 1924) – Material examined: [S1.01] Malaise trap: 28.VIII–4.IX.1998, 1 ♂; 2–31.X.1998, 1 ♂; 954 m, near Bosnek Village, near Akademik Cave, MSS traps: 6.VI–2.XI.2013, 1 ♀. Westpalaeartic; known from Europe, Macaronesia (Azores) and Asia (Iran). For the Balkan Peninsula also known from North Macedonia (Langourov, 1999). Published for the mountain by Langourov et al. (2014).

79. *Megaselia breviterga* (Lundbeck, 1920) – Material examined: 900 m, near Bosnek Village, near Popov Izvor Karst spring, MSS traps: 6.VI–2.X.2013, 18 ♂♂, 4 ♀♀; 1118 m, near Bosnek Village, Zhivata Voda Cave, soil traps: 13.VIII–15.XI.2013, 2 ♂♂. Holarctic species. For the Balkan Peninsula also known from Croatia (Schmitz, 1924). Other localities in Bulgaria: Western Rhodope Mts (Langourov, 2010).

** 80. *Megaselia brunneipennis* Costa, 1857 – Material examined: [S1.01] Malaise trap: 18–28.VIII.1998, 1 ♂; 28.VIII–4.IX.1998, 1 ♂ • [E1.05], tree traps: 1.IX–1.X.1998, 1 ♂ • [N1.06] soil traps: 1.VIII–1.IX.1999, 1 ♂. Westpalaeartic species, known from Europe and Macaronesia (Canary Is). New region: Balkan Peninsula – Bulgaria.

** 81. *Megaselia campestris* (Wood, 1908) – Material examined: [S1.01] Malaise trap: 2–31.X.1998, 1 ♂ • [E1.05], tree traps: 1.VII–1.VIII.1998, 1 ♂ • [N1.06] soil traps: 1.VII–1.VIII.1999, 1 ♀. European species. New region: Balkan Peninsula – Bulgaria.

82. *Megaselia ciliata* (Zetterstedt, 1848) – Material examined: [N1.01] Malaise trap: 10–18.V.1997, 1 ♂ • [E1.05]: 1.VIII–1.IX.1998, 1 ♂, 1 ♀, soil traps; 1.IX–1.X.1998, 2 ♂♂, 1 ♀, tree traps; 1.X–1.XI.1998, 1 ♂, 1 ♀, tree traps; 1.VII–1.VIII.1999, 1 ♂, 1 ♀, soil traps; 1.VIII–1.IX.1999, 2 ♂♂, tree traps; 2 ♂♂, 1 ♀, soil traps; 1.IX–1.X.1999, 1 ♂, tree traps; 2 ♂♂, soil traps; 1.X–1.XI.1999, 2 ♀♀, tree traps • [N1.05] Malaise trap: 5–12.VI.1998, 1 ♂ • [N1.06]: 1.VII–1.VIII.1998, 1 ♀, soil traps; 1.VIII–1.IX.1998, 1 ♂, tree traps; 6.X.1998, 1 ♀; 1.VIII–1.IX.1999, 2 ♂♂, tree traps; 1.IX–1.X.1999, 1 ♀, soil traps; 1.X–1.XI.1999, 1 ♀, tree traps • [E2.01]:

1.V–1.VI.1998, 2 ♂♂, 2 ♀♀, tree traps; 1.VI–1.VII.1998, 1 ♂, soil traps; 2.X.1998, 1 ♀; 1.VIII–1.IX.1999, 2 ♀♀, tree traps; 1.IX–1.X.1999, 1 ♂, 1 ♀, tree traps • [E3.02]: 1.IX–1.X.1998, 1 ♀, soil traps; 1.V–1.VII.1999, 1 ♀, tree traps; 1 ♂, soil traps; 1.VI–1.VII.1999, 1 ♂, soil traps; 1.VIII–1.IX.1999, 2 ♀♀, tree traps; 1 ♂, soil traps; 1.IX–1.X.1999, 4 ♂♂, 5 ♀♀, tree traps; 3 ♂♂, 3 ♀♀, soil traps • [W3.04] soil traps: 6.IX–4.X.1999, 1 ♂ • [E3.04] soil traps: 1.IX–1.X.1999, 1 ♀. European species, reported for the Balkan Peninsula from Bosnia-Herzegovina (Strobl, 1898) and Montenegro (Langourov, 2004a). Other localities in Bulgaria: Sofia Plain (Langourov, 2004c).

** 83. *Megaselia coei* Schmitz, 1938 – Material examined: [N1.06], tree traps: 1.IX–1.X.1998, 1 ♂ • [E3.04]: 5.VIII.1999, 2 ♂♂, 1 ♀, on racemes of *Angelica sylvestris* L. European species, known from Austria, Great Britain and Poland. New region: Balkan Peninsula – Bulgaria.

** 84. *Megaselia conformis* (Wood, 1909) – Material examined: [E3.02], tree traps: 1.VIII–1.IX.1998, 1 ♂, 1 ♀. European species. New region: Balkan Peninsula – Bulgaria.

* 85. *Megaselia crassicosta* (Strobl, 1892) – Material examined: [N1.03]: 30.V.1993, 1 ♀ • [E1.05] soil traps: 1.IX–1.X.1998, 1 ♂; 1.V–1.VI.1999, 1 ♀; 1.VII–1.VIII.1999, 1 ♂ • [E2.01], tree traps: 1.VI–1.VII.1999, 1 ♀ • [N3.02]: 12.VI–4.VII.1999, 1 ♀ • [W3.02] soil traps: 5.VI–3.VII.1999, 1 ♀ • [E3.04] soil traps: 1.IV–1.VII.1999, 1 ♀; 1.IV–1.VIII.1999, 1 ♀. European species, reported for the Balkan Peninsula from Croatia (Schmitz, 1924e) and Montenegro (Langourov, 2004a).

* 86. *Megaselia crassipes* (Wood, 1909) – Material examined: [E1.05]: 1.XI.1998–15.IV.1999, 2 ♂♂, tree traps; 1.VII–1.VIII.1999, 1 ♂, soil traps. Holarctic; known from Europe and North America. For the Balkans known from Montenegro (Langourov, 2004a).

87. *Megaselia curvicapilla* Schmitz, 1947 – Material examined: [S1.01] Malaise trap: 18–28.VIII.1998, 1 ♂; 28.VIII–4.IX.1998, 3 ♂♂; 2–31.X.1998, 2 ♂♂; 17–30.IV.1999, 1 ♂ • [N1.06] soil traps: 1.V–1.VI.1999, 1 ♂ • [E3.03] soil traps: 5.VII–6.VIII.1999, 1 ♂ • [E3.04] soil traps: 1.IV–1.IX.1999, 1 ♂. Westpalaearctic species, known from Europe and Asia (Israel, Iran). For the Balkan Peninsula also known from North Macedonia (Langourov, 1999). Other localities in Bulgaria: Western Rhodope Mts (Langourov, 2010).

88. *Megaselia dahli* (Becker, 1901) – Material examined: [S1.01] Malaise trap: 2–31.X.1998, 3 ♂♂ •

[N1.06], tree traps: 1.VI–1.VII.1999, 1 ♂. European species, known for the Balkan Peninsula from North Macedonia (Langourov, 1999) and Montenegro (Langourov, 2004a). Other localities in Bulgaria: Western Rhodope Mts (Langourov, 2010).

* 89. *Megaselia differens* Schmitz, 1948 – Material examined: [E3.02], soil traps: 1.V–1.VII.1999, 1 ♂. Westpalaearctic species, known from Europe and Asia (Russian Far East). For the Balkan Peninsula also known from North Macedonia (Langourov, 1999).

* 90. *Megaselia discreta* (Wood, 1909) – Material examined: [E1.05]: 1.VIII–1.XI.1999, 1 ♂, 2 ♀♀, tree traps; 1 ♂, soil traps; 1.IX–1.X.1999, 1 ♂, 1 ♀, soil traps. European species, known for the Balkan Peninsula from Croatia (Schmitz, 1924).

91. *Megaselia diversa* (Wood, 1909) – Material examined: [E1.04]: 20.VIII.1992, 1 ♀ • [E1.05]: 1.VIII–1.IX.1998, 1 ♂, soil traps; 1.IX–1.X.1998, 1 ♂, soil traps; 1.V–1.VI.1999, 1 ♀, tree traps; 1.VII–1.VIII.1999, 1 ♂, tree traps; 1.VIII–1.IX.1999, 2 ♂♂, 3 ♀♀, tree traps; 1.IX–1.X.1999, 1 ♂, tree traps • [N1.06]: 1.VIII–1.IX.1998, 1 ♂, soil traps; 1.X–1.XI.1998, 2 ♂♂, 1 ♀, tree traps; 15.IV–1.V.1999, 1 ♀, tree traps; 1.V–1.VI.1999, 1 ♂, soil traps; 1.VI–1.VII.1999, 1 ♂, tree traps; 3 ♂♂, soil traps; 1.VIII–1.IX.1999, 1 ♂, soil traps • between [N1.06] to [N1.07]: 19.IV.1993, 1 ♂ • [E2.01]: 1.VII–1.VIII.1998, 1 ♀, tree traps; 1.VIII–1.IX.1998, 1 ♂, tree traps; 1 ♂, 2 ♀♀, soil traps; 1.VIII–1.IX.1999, 1 ♂, tree traps • between [E2.01] to [E2.02]: 17.X.1992, 1 ♂ • [N2.02]: 27.VIII.1992, 1 ♂ • [N2.03]: 31.V.1998, 1 ♂ • 1820–1870 m, between Edelvais Chalet to Konyarnika place, spruce wood: 2.VI.1996, 1 ♂ • [W3.01]: 2.VI.1996, 1 ♂ • [E3.02]: 1.VII–1.VIII.1998, 1 ♂, tree traps; 1.VIII–1.IX.1998, 1 ♀, tree traps; 1.IX–1.X.1998, 1 ♂, 3 ♀♀, tree traps; 1.V–1.VI.1999, 2 ♂♂, 1 ♀, tree traps; 1.VI–1.VII.1999, 2 ♂♂, 5 ♀♀, tree traps; 1.VII–1.VIII.1999, 1 ♂, 1 ♀, soil traps; 1.VIII–1.IX.1999, 1 ♂, tree traps; 1 ♂, 1 ♀, soil traps; 1.IX–1.X.1999, 2 ♂♂, tree traps; 1.XI.1999–1.V.2000, 1 ♂, soil traps • [E3.03] soil traps: 5.VII–6.VIII.1999, 1 ♂, 1 ♀ • [E3.04] soil traps: 15.V–1.VI.1999, 4 ♂♂, 1 ♀; 1.VI–1.VII.1999, 1 ♂ • [S4.02] soil traps: 7.VIII–6.IX.1999, 1 ♂ • 2280 m, Cherni Vruh, subalpine zone: 2.VI.1996, 1 ♂. Holarctic; known from Europe, North Africa (Tunisia), Asia (Israel, Russian Far East) and North America. For the Balkan Peninsula known from Croatia (Schmitz, 1924; Coe, 1956), other parts of the former Yugoslavia (Schmitz & Beyer, 1965), Montenegro (Langourov, 2004a). Other localities

ies in Bulgaria: Kresna Gorge (Langourov & Sakalian, 2001), E Rhodope Mts (Langourov, 2004b), W Rhodope Mts (Langourov, 2010).

** 92. *Megaselia dubitalis* (Wood, 1908) – Material examined: [N1.05] Malaise trap: 5–12.VI.1998, 3 ♂♂ • [N1.06] soil traps: 1.V–1.VI.1999, 3 ♂♂. European species, known from Middle and North Europe. New region: Balkan Peninsula – Bulgaria.

** 93. *Megaselia eccoptomera* Schmitz, 1927 – Material examined: [E2.01], tree traps: 1.VII–1.VIII.1999, 1 ♂ • [W3.01]: 2.VI.1996, 1 ♂ • [E3.02], soil traps: 1.V–1.VI.1999, 1 ♂; 1.VI–1.VII.1999, 6 ♂♂, 1 ♀. Holarctic species, known from Europe and North America. New region: Balkan Peninsula – Bulgaria.

* 94. *Megaselia elongata* (Wood, 1914) – Material examined: [N1.05] Malaise trap: 5–12.VI.1998, 1 ♂. Westpalaearctic; known from Europe and Asia (Israel). Balkan Peninsula: Croatia (Schmitz, 1924 as *Aphiochaeta cuspidata* Schmitz, 1919).

95. *Megaselia emarginata* (Wood, 1908) – Material examined: [N1.01] Malaise trap: 10–18.V.1997, 1 ♂ • [S2.01]: 16–23.V.2000, 5 ♂♂ • [N1.05] Malaise trap: 29.V–5.VI.1998, 1 ♂; 5–12.VI.1998, 1 ♂; 3–8.VII.1998, 1 ♂. European species, for the Balkan Peninsula known from Croatia (Coe, 1956) and Montenegro (Langourov, 2004a). Other localities in Bulgaria: Sofia Plain (Langourov, 2004b).

** 96. *Megaselia errata* (Wood, 1912) – Material examined: [N1.01] Malaise trap: 10–18.V.1997, 1 ♂ • [E1.05] soil traps: 1.VIII–1.IX.1998, 1 ♂, 1 ♀. European species, known from Middle Europe. New region: Balkan Peninsula – Bulgaria.

97. *Megaselia flava* (Fallen, 1823) – Material examined: [E1.05]: 28.VII.1993, 1 ♂; 1.VIII–1.IX.1998, 1 ♂, tree traps; 1.IX–1.X.1998, 1 ♂, soil traps • 1260–1360 m, near Esperanto Chalet, mixed wood: 3.IX.1992, 1 ♂ • between [E1.05] to [E1.06]: 27.VIII.1992, 1 ♂ • [N1.05] Malaise trap: 3–8.VII.1998, 1 ♂ • [N1.06] soil traps: 1.VII–1.VIII.1999, 3 ♀♀. Holarctic-Oriental species, known from Europe, Asia (Israel, Japan), North America and Oriental Region. For the Balkan Peninsula known from Bosnia-Herzegovina (Strobl, 1898), Croatia (Coe, 1956), North Macedonia (Coe, 1956; Langourov, 1999) and Montenegro (Langourov, 2004a). Other localities in Bulgaria: Western Rhodope Mts (Langourov, 2010).

98. *Megaselia flavicans* Schmitz, 1935 – Material examined: [N1.01] Malaise trap: 10–18.V.1997, 2 ♂♂

• [S1.01] Malaise trap: 17–30.IV.1999, 2 ♂♂ • [E1.05], tree traps: 1.VIII–1.IX.1998, 1 ♂ • [N1.06] soil traps: 1.IX–1.X.1999, 1 ♂, 1 ♀; 1.XI.1999–1.IV.2000, 1 ♂. Westpalaearctic; known from Europe and Asia (Turkey. Balkan Peninsula: Croatia (Schmitz, 1953), North Macedonia (Coe, 1956), Greece (Disney, 1991). Bulgaria: Kresna Gorge (Langourov & Sakalian, 2001).

** 99. *Megaselia flavicoxa* (Zetterstedt, 1848) – Material examined: [E1.05] soil traps: 1.VIII–1.IX.1999, 1 ♂. European species. New region: Balkan Peninsula – Bulgaria.

** 100. *Megaselia frameata* Schmitz, 1927 – Material examined: [E1.06]: 20.VIII.1992, 1 ♂. European species. New region: Balkan Peninsula – Bulgaria.

** 101. *Megaselia frontalis* (Wood, 1909) – Material examined: [S1.01] Malaise trap: 18–28.VIII.1998, 1 ♂. European species, known from Middle Europe. New region: Balkan Peninsula – Bulgaria.

** 102. *Megaselia fungivora* (Wood, 1909) – Material examined: [E1.05], tree traps: 1.VII–1.VIII.1999, 1 ♂. Holarctic species, known from Middle and North Europe and North America. New region: Balkan Peninsula – Bulgaria.

103. *Megaselia fusca* (Wood, 1909) – Material examined: [E1.05], tree traps: 1.IX–1.X.1998, 1 ♂; 1.VII–1.VIII.1999, 1 ♂, soil traps; • [N1.06] soil traps: 1.IX–1.X.1999, 2 ♂♂, 1 ♀ • [E3.02], soil traps: 1.VI–1.VII.1999, 1 ♂; 1.VII–1.VIII.1999, 1 ♂ • [W3.03] soil traps: 12.VI–3.VII.1999, 1 ♂ • [E3.04] soil traps: 1.VI–1.VII.1999, 5 ♂♂; 1.VII–1.VIII.1999, 1 ♂. Palaearctic; known from Europe and Asia (Russian Far East). For the Balkan Peninsula also known from Bosnia-Herzegovina (Schmitz, 1928), Croatia (Coe, 1956) and Montenegro (Langourov, 2004a). Other localities in Bulgaria: Western Stara Planina Mts (Czerny, 1930) and Vitosha Mt (Langourov, 2001).

** 104. *Megaselia fuscipalpis* (Lundbeck, 1920) – Material examined: [N1.06] soil traps: 1.V–1.VI.1999, 1 ♂. European species, known from Middle and North Europe. New region: Balkan Peninsula – Bulgaria.

** 105. *Megaselia fuscovariana* Schmitz, 1933 – Material examined: [N1.01] Malaise trap: 10–18.V.1997, 1 ♂. European species, known from Middle Europe. New region: Balkan Peninsula – Bulgaria.

106. *Megaselia giraudii* (Egger, 1862) – Material examined: [N1.01] Malaise trap: 10–18.V.1997, 5 ♂♂, 1 ♀ • [S1.01] Malaise trap: 18–28.VIII.1998, 1 ♂; 28.VIII–4.IX.1998, 4 ♂♂; 2–31.X.1998, 4 ♂♂ • [E1.05]: 1.VII–1.VIII.1998, 1 ♂, tree traps;

1.VIII–1.IX.1998, 1 ♂, 1 ♀, soil traps; 1.VII–1.VIII.1999, 1 ♂, tree traps • [N1.05] Malaise trap: 3–8.VII.1998, 1 ♂ • [N1.06]: 1.V–1.VI.1999, 1 ♂, soil traps; 1.VII–1.VIII.1999, 2 ♂♂, tree traps • [E2.01]: 1.VIII–1.IX.1998, 1 ♂, 1 ♀, soil traps; 1.VIII–1.IX.1999, 1 ♂, tree traps • [N2.02]: 30.V.1993, 1 ♂ • [E3.02], tree traps: 1.VII–1.VIII.1999, 1 ♂. Holarctic species, known from Europe, Macaronesia, Asia (Israel, Iran, Russian Far East) and North America. For the Balkan Peninsula also known from Bosnia-Herzegovina (Strobl, 1898), Croatia, Serbia (Schmitz, 1924) and North Macedonia (Coe, 1956). Other localities in Bulgaria: Sofia Plain (Langourov, 2004b) and Western Rhodope Mts (Langourov, 2010).

** 107. *Megaselia glabrifrons* (Wood, 1909) – Material examined: [N1.05] Malaise trap: 5–12.VI.1998, 2 ♂♂ • [N1.06] soil traps: 1.VII–1.VIII.1998, 1 ♂; 1.V–1.VI.1999, 3 ♂♂; 1.VI–1.VII.1999, 1 ♂ • [E3.02]: 1.VI–1.VII.1999, 1 ♂, tree traps; 10 ♂♂, soil traps; 1.VII–1.VIII.1999, 1 ♂, tree traps. Holarctic species, known from Europe and North America. New region: Balkan Peninsula – Bulgaria.

** 108. *Megaselia gregaria* (Wood, 1910) – Material examined: [S1.01] Malaise trap: 2–31.X.1998, 1 ♂. European species. New region: Balkan Peninsula – Bulgaria.

109. *Megaselia halterata* (Wood, 1910) – Material examined: [S1.01] Malaise trap: 18–28.VIII.1998, 1 ♂; 28.VIII–4.IX.1998, 1 ♂. Subcosmopolitan species, known from Europe, Macaronesia, North Africa, Asia and North America, introduced to Australia and New Zealand. Other localities in Bulgaria: Western Stara Planina Mts, Sofia Plain and Vitosha Mt (Langourov, 2001).

** 110. *Megaselia hirsuta* (Wood, 1910) – Material examined: [S1.01] Malaise trap: 18–28.VIII.1998, 1 ♂ • [E1.05] soil traps: 1.VII–1.VIII.1999, 1 ♂ • [N1.06] soil traps: 1.VII–1.VIII.1998, 2 ♂♂, 1 ♀ • [E2.01], tree traps: 1.VII–1.VIII.1998, 1 ♂ • [E3.02], soil traps: 1.V–1.VI.1999, 1 ♂, 1 ♀. Westpalaearctic species, known from Europe and Macaronesia. New region: Balkan Peninsula – Bulgaria.

111. *Megaselia hirticaudata* (Wood, 1910) – Material examined: [N1.06] soil traps: 15.IV–1.V.1999, 1 ♂ • [E2.01], tree traps: 1.VIII–1.IX.1999, 1 ♂. Westpalaearctic species, known from Europe and Asia (Iran). For the Balkan Peninsula also known from Montenegro (Langourov, 2004a as *M. capronata* Schmitz, 1940). Other localities in Bulgaria: Eastern Rhodope Mts (Langourov, 2004c).

112. *Megaselia hirtiventris* (Wood, 1909) – Material examined: [E1.05] soil traps: 1.X–1.XI.1998, 1 ♂. Palaearctic species, known from Europe and Asia (Russian Far East). Other localities in Bulgaria: Sofia Plain (Langourov, 2004b) and Eastern Rhodope Mts (Langourov, 2004c).

** 113. *Megaselia horsfieldi* Disney, 1986 – Material examined: [E3.02], tree traps: 1.VIII–1.IX.1999, 1 ♂. European species, till now known only from Great Britain. New region: Balkan Peninsula – Bulgaria.

** 114. *Megaselia hyalipennis* (Wood, 1912) – Material examined: [E2.01], tree traps: 1.VIII–1.IX.1999, 3 ♂♂. Palaearctic species, known from Middle and North Europe and Asia (Russian Far East). New region: Balkan Peninsula – Bulgaria.

** 115. *Megaselia hypopygialis* (Lundbeck, 1920) – Material examined: [E1.05] soil traps: 1.VIII–1.IX.1999, 1 ♂. European; known from Middle Europe. New region: Balkan Peninsula – Bulgaria.

** 116. *Megaselia intonsa* Schmitz, 1948 – Material examined: [E1.05]: 1.VII–1.VIII.1998, 1 ♀, tree traps; 1.V–1.VI.1999, 2 ♀♀, soil traps • [N1.06] soil traps: 1.V–1.VI.1999, 1 ♂ • [E1.06]: 20.VIII.1992, 1 ♂ • 1500 m, E of Septemvri Chalet, beech wood, tree traps: 3–10.VII.1998, 2 ♂♂ • [E2.01]: 20.VIII.1992, 1 ♂; 1.VII–1.VIII.1999, 5 ♂♂, tree traps • [N3.02]: 4.VII–6.VIII.1999, 7 ♂♂, 6 ♀♀ • [E3.02]: 1.VII–1.VIII.1998, 10 ♂♂, 5 ♀♀, tree traps; 1.VIII–1.IX.1998, 1 ♂, tree traps; 1.VI–1.VII.1999, 16 ♂♂, 1 ♀, soil traps; 1.VII–1.VIII.1999, 219 ♂♂, numerous ♀♀, tree traps; 34 ♂♂, 32 ♀♀, soil traps • [N3.03] soil traps: 4.VII–6.VIII.1999, 1 ♂, 4 ♀♀ • [E3.03] soil traps: 12.VI–5.VII.1999, 3 ♂♂, 2 ♀♀; 5.VII–6.VIII.1999, 18 ♂♂, 7 ♀♀ • [W3.02] soil traps: 5.VI–3.VII.1999, 3 ♂♂; 3.VII–7.VIII.1999, 41 ♂♂, 16 ♀♀ • [W3.03] soil traps: 3.VII–7.VIII.1999, 19 ♂♂, 13 ♀♀; 7.VIII–6.IX.1999, 1 ♂ • [W3.04] soil traps: 5.IV–3.VII.1999, 3 ♂♂; 3.IV–7.VIII.1999, 53 ♂♂, 12 ♀♀ • [W3.05] soil traps: 3.VII–7.VIII.1999, 15 ♂♂, 4 ♀♀ • [E3.04] soil traps: 1.VII–1.VIII.1999, 30 ♂♂, 4 ♀♀; 1.VIII–1.IX.1999, 2 ♂♂, 1 ♀; 1.XI.1999–1.V.2000, 3 ♂♂, 4 ♀♀ • [W3.06] soil traps: 3.VII–6.VIII.1999, 28 ♂♂, 17 ♀♀; 7.VIII–6.IX.1999, 2 ♂♂ • [S4.02] soil traps: 3.VII–7.VIII.1999, 1 ♂ • [S4.03]: 5.VII–6.VIII.1999, 9 ♂♂, 2 ♀♀. Palaearctic species, known from North Europe and Asia (Russian Far East). New region: Balkan Peninsula – Bulgaria.

117. *Megaselia involuta* (Wood, 1910) – Material examined: [E2.01], soil traps: 1.VII–1.VIII.1999, 1 ♂. European species, known for the Balkan Peninsula

from Greece and Serbia (Schmitz, 1924). Other localities in Bulgaria: Kresna Gorge (Langourov & Sakalian, 2001) and Western Rhodope Mts (Langourov, 2010).

118. *Megaselia largifrontalis* Schmitz, 1939 – Material examined: 900 m, near Bosnek Village, near Popov Izvor Karst spring, MSS traps: 6.VI–2.X.2013, 2 ♂♂, 1 ♀. Palaearctic-Afrotropical species, known from Europe, Asia (Yemen) and Afrotropical Region (St Helena Island, introduced). Published for the mountain by Langourov et al. (2014).

119. *Megaselia lata* (Wood, 1910) – Material examined: [S2.01]: 18.VIII–1.IX.2000, 1 ♂ • [E1.05]: 1.VIII–1.IX.1998, 3 ♂♂, soil traps; 1.X–1.XI.1998, 1 ♂, soil traps; 1.VII–1.VIII.1999, 3 ♂♂, 4 ♀♀, soil traps; 1.VIII–1.IX.1999, 1 ♂, soil traps; 1.IX–1.X.1999, 1 ♂, tree traps; 1 ♂, 1 ♀, soil traps • [N1.06]: 1.VII–1.VIII.1998, 8 ♂♂, 12 ♀♀, soil traps; 1.IX–1.X.1998, 1 ♂, tree traps; 1.V–1.VI.1999, 1 ♂, soil traps; 1.VI–1.VII.1999, 1 ♂, soil traps; 1.VII–1.VIII.1999, 1 ♂, 3 ♀♀, soil traps; 1.VIII–1.IX.1999, 1 ♂, tree traps • [E2.01]: 1.VIII–1.IX.1998, 1 ♂, soil traps; 1.IX–1.X.1998, 1 ♂, soil traps; 1.VIII–1.IX.1999, 2 ♂♂, tree traps; 1 ♂, soil traps • [E3.02]: 1.VII–1.VIII.1999, 1 ♂, tree traps; 1 ♂, soil traps • [W3.05] soil traps: 7.VIII–6.IX.1999, 1 ♂. Westpalaearctic species, known from Europe and Macaronesia. For the Balkan Peninsula also known from Slovenia (Schmitz, 1928) and Montenegro (Langourov, 2004a). Other localities in Bulgaria: Western Rhodope Mts (Langourov, 2010).

* 120. *Megaselia latifemorata* (Becker, 1901) – Material examined: [N1.01] Malaise trap: 10–18.V.1997, 1 ♂; 28.IV–1.V.1998, 1 ♂, 1 ♀; 12–17.V.1998, 3 ♂♂ • 1260–1360 m, near Esperanto Chalet, mixed wood: 30.V.1993, 2 ♂♂, 1 ♀ • [E1.05]: 1.VIII–1.IX.1998, 1 ♀, tree traps; 1.VII–1.VIII.1999, 1 ♂, soil traps; 1.V–1.VI.1999, 1 ♀, soil traps; 1.VII–1.VIII.1999, 1 ♂, tree traps • [N1.05] Malaise trap: 29.V–5.VI.1998, 1 ♂; 5–12.VI.1998, 1 ♂ • [N1.06]: 30.V.1993, 1 ♂, 1 ♀; 1.VII–1.VIII.1998, 1 ♂, soil traps; 15.IV–1.V.1999, 1 ♂, tree traps; 1.V–1.VI.1999, 3 ♂♂, soil traps; 1.VI–1.VII.1999, 1 ♂, soil traps • between [N1.06] to [N1.07]: 30.V.1993, 1 ♂, 2 ♀♀ • between [E1.06] to [E2.01]: 30.V.1993, 1 ♀ • between [N1.07] to [N2.01]: 30.V.1993, 1 ♂ • 1500 m, E of Septemvri Chalet, beech wood, tree traps: 3–10.VII.1998, 1 ♀ • [E2.01]: 1.VIII–1.IX.1998, 1 ♂, soil traps; 1.V–1.VI.1999, 2 ♂♂, 1 ♀, tree traps • between [N2.02] to [N2.03]: 30.V.1993, 2 ♂♂ • [N2.03]: 31.V.1998, 2 ♂♂ • 1820 m, near Goli

Vruh, subalpine zone (leg. N. Simov): 27.V.2000, 1 ♀ • [E3.02]: 1.V–1.VI.1999, 1 ♀, tree traps; 3 ♂♂, 1 ♀, soil traps; 1.VI–1.VII.1999, 1 ♀, tree traps; 1.VII–1.VIII.1999, 2 ♂♂, 2 ♀♀, soil traps; 1.VIII–1.IX.1999, 1 ♀, tree traps • [W3.02] soil traps: 5.VI–3.VII.1999, 1 ♂ • [W3.04] soil traps: 5.IV–3.VII.1999, 1 ♀ • [E3.04] soil traps: 15.V–1.VI.1999, 2 ♂♂; 1.VI–1.VII.1999, 15 ♂♂, 3 ♀♀; 1.VII–1.VIII.1999, 8 ♂♂, 1 ♀; 1.XI.1999–1.V.2000, 1 ♂, 1 ♀. Palaearctic species, known from Europe and Asia (Japan). For the Balkan Peninsula known from Croatia and Slovenia (Schmitz, 1924), North Macedonia (Langourov, 1999) and Montenegro (Langourov, 2004a).

121. *Megaselia latifrons* (Wood, 1910) – Material examined: [N1.06]: 1.V–1.VI.1999, 3 ♂♂, soil traps; 1.VI–1.VII.1999, 1 ♂, tree traps • [N3.01]: 3.IX.1992, 1 ♂ • [E3.02], soil traps: 1.V–1.VI.1999, 1 ♂. Westpalaearctic species, known from Europe and Asia (Israel). For the Balkan Peninsula known from North Macedonia (Coe, 1956; Colyer, 1956 under the synonym *Megaselia propior* Colyer, 1956) and Montenegro (Langourov, 2004a). In Bulgaria: Rila Mts (Schmitz, 1953) and W Rhodope Mts (Langourov, 2010).

122. *Megaselia ledburicensis* (Brues, 1915) – Material examined: [S1.01] Malaise trap: 18–28.VIII.1998, 3 ♂♂. Westpalaearctic species, known from Europe and Asia (Israel, Iran). Other localities in Bulgaria: Western Rhodope Mts (Langourov, 2010 as *Megaselia subfuscipes* Schmitz, 1935).

* 123. *Megaselia longiseta* (Wood, 1909) – Material examined: [N2.01]: 21.VII.1992, 1 ♂. Holarctic species, known from Europe, Macaronesia, Asia (Iran, Russian Far East) and North America. For the Balkan Peninsula known from Slovenia (Schmitz, 1928) and Montenegro (Langourov, 2004a).

124. *Megaselia lucifrons* (Schmitz, 1918) – Material examined: [N1.06] soil traps: 1.VII–1.VIII.1998, 1 ♂ • [E2.01]: 1.IX–1.X.1998, 2 ♂♂, tree traps; 1.VIII–1.IX.1999, 1 ♂, soil traps. European species. Other localities in Bulgaria: Western Rhodope Mts (Langourov, 2010).

125. *Megaselia lutea* (Meigen, 1830) – Material examined: [E1.04]: 20.VIII.1992, 1 ♂ • [N1.05] Malaise trap: 26.VI–3.VII.1998, 1 ♀ • between [E2.01] to [E2.03]: 20.VIII.1992, 1 ♂. Holarctic species, for the Balkan Peninsula known from Croatia (Langhoffer, 1919), North Macedonia (Coe, 1956) and Montenegro (Langourov, 2004a). Other localities in Bulgaria: Western Rhodope Mts (Langourov, 2010).

126. *Megaselia mallochii* (Wood, 1909) – Material examined: [E1.05], tree traps: 1.VII–1.VIII.1998, 1 ♂; 1.VIII–1.IX.1998, 1 ♂; 1.IX–1.X.1998, 3 ♂♂, 4 ♀♀; 1.XI.1998–15.IV.1999, 2 ♂♂, 3 ♀♀; 1.VII–1.VIII.1999, 1 ♂; 1.IX–1.X.1999, 1 ♂, 5 ♀♀; 1.XI.1999–1.IV.2000, 2 ♂♂ • [N1.06]: 1.V–1.VI.1998, 1 ♂, 5 ♀♀, soil traps; 1 ♀, tree traps; 1.VII–1.VIII.1998, 1 ♂, soil traps; 1 ♂, tree traps; 1.X–1.XI.1998, 1 ♂, tree traps; 1.XI.1998–15.IV.1999, 7 ♂♂, 3 ♀♀, tree traps; 15.IV–1.V.1999, 8 ♂♂, 10 ♀♀, tree traps; 32 ♂♂, 16 ♀♀, soil traps; 1.V–1.VI.1999, 3 ♂♂, soil traps • [E2.01]: 1.VIII–1.IX.1998, 1 ♀, tree traps; 1.IX–1.X.1998, 1 ♀, tree traps; 1.VII–1.VIII.1999, 4 ♂♂, tree traps; 1.VIII–1.IX.1999, 1 ♂, tree traps; 1 ♂, 1 ♀, soil traps; 1.IX–1.X.1999, 1 ♂, tree traps; 1.X–1.XI.1999, 1 ♂, tree traps • [E3.02]: 1.VII–1.VIII.1998, 3 ♂♂, 2 ♀♀, tree traps; 1.VII–1.VIII.1999, 1 ♂, soil traps; 1.VIII–1.IX.1999, 1 ♂, 1 ♀, tree traps; 2 ♂♂, 2 ♀♀, soil traps; 1.IX–1.X.1999, 1 ♂, soil traps • [E3.04] soil traps: 15.V–1.VI.1999, 1 ♂, 3 ♀♀ • [W3.06] soil traps: 6.VI–3.VII.1999, 1 ♂. European; other localities in Bulgaria: Western Rhodope Mts (Langourov, 2010).

* 127. *Megaselia manicata* (Wood, 1910) – Material examined: [N1.06] soil traps: 1.V–1.VI.1999, 3 ♂♂. Westpalaeartic species, known from Europe, North Africa (Tunisia) and Macaronesia. For the Balkan Peninsula known from Slovenia, Montenegro (Schmitz, 1928) and North Macedonia (Coe, 1956).

128. *Megaselia meconicera* (Speiser, 1925) – Material examined: [E1.04]: 20.VIII.1992, 2 ♂♂ • [N1.05] Malaise trap: 5–12.VI.1998, 1 ♂ • [N1.06]: 20.VIII.1992, 2 ♂♂ • [E1.06]: 20.VIII.1992, 1 ♂ • [N1.07]: 20.VIII.1992, 1 ♀ • [E2.01], tree traps: 1.VIII–1.IX.1998, 2 ♂♂, 2 ♀♀. Holarctic; for the Balkan Peninsula known from Albania (Schmitz, 1928) and Montenegro (Langourov, 2004a). Other localities in Bulgaria: E Rhodope Mts (Langourov, 2004b) and W Rhodope Mts (Langourov, 2010).

* 129. *Megaselia melanocephala* (von Roser, 1840) – Material examined: [S1.01] Malaise trap: 4–10.VIII.1998, 1 ♂; 17–30.IV.1999, 1 ♂. Euro-Mediterranean; known from Middle and South Europe, North Africa (Tunisia) and Asia (Israel). For the Balkan Peninsula known from Croatia (Schmitz, 1924).

130. *Megaselia nigriceps* (Loew, 1866) – Material examined: [N1.04]: 25.IX.1992, 1 ♂ • [E1.05]: 1.VII–1.VIII.1998, 1 ♀, tree traps; 1.IX–1.X.1998, 1 ♂, 3 ♀♀, tree traps; 1.VII–1.VIII.1999, 1 ♂, soil traps; 1.VIII–1.IX.1999, 7 ♂♂, 2 ♀♀, tree traps; 2 ♂♂,

soil traps • between [E1.05] to [E1.06]: 27.VIII.1992, 1 ♀ • [N1.06]: 1.VII–1.VIII.1998, 1 ♂, soil traps; 3 ♂♂, 2 ♀♀, tree traps; 1.VIII–1.IX.1998, 1 ♂, 1 ♀, soil traps; 13 ♂♂, tree traps; 1.VI–1.VII.1999, 1 ♀, tree traps; 1.VII–1.VIII.1999, 1 ♂, soil traps; 1.VIII–1.IX.1999, 1 ♂, tree traps • between [E2.01] to [E2.03]: 20.VIII.1992, 1 ♂ • [E2.01]: 20.VIII.1992, 1 ♀; 27.VIII.1992, 1 ♂; 1.VIII–1.IX.1998, 1 ♂, tree traps; 1.IX–1.X.1998, 2 ♂♂, tree traps; 1.VIII–1.IX.1999, 1 ♂, tree traps; 1 ♂, soil traps • between [E2.01] to [E2.02]: 27.VIII.1992, 1 ♂; 3.IX.1992, 1 ♂ • [N2.02]: 3.IX.1992, 1 ♂ • between [N2.02] to [N2.03]: 27.VIII.1992, 1 ♂ • [N2.03]: 20.VIII.1992, 1 ♂ • 1830 m, Bistrishko Branishte Reserve, near Fizkulturnik Chalet, subalpine zone (leg. V. Beschovski): 8.X.1981, 1 ♂ • 1840 m, near Aleko Chalet, spruce wood: 12.IX.1999, 1 ♂ feeding on sugar syrup. Holarctic; known from Europe, Asia (Japan, Russian Far East) and North America. Reported for the Balkan Peninsula as *Megaselia projecta* (Becker) from Croatia (Schmitz, 1924), Bulgaria (Schmitz, 1953a, without locality) and Montenegro (Langourov, 2004a).

** 131. *Megaselia nigripalpis* (Lundbeck, 1920) – Material examined: [N1.04]: 30.V.1993, 1 ♂ • 1260–1360 m, near Esperanto Chalet, mixed wood: 30.V.1993, 1 ♂ • [E3.02]: 1.VIII–1.IX.1999, 3 ♂♂, tree traps. European species, till now known from Germany, Denmark, Norway and Finland. New region: Balkan Peninsula – Bulgaria.

** 132. *Megaselia obscuripennis* (Wood, 1909) – Material examined: [N1.05] 1150 m: 21.VII.1992, 1 ♂ • [E1.05] soil traps: 1.VIII–1.IX.1998, 1 ♂ • [N1.05] Malaise trap: 5–12.VI.1998, 2 ♂, 1 ♀ • [N3.02]: 12.VI–4.VII.1999, 1 ♂. European species, known from Middle and North Europe. New region: Balkan Peninsula – Bulgaria.

133. *Megaselia oxybelorum* Schmitz, 1928 – Material examined: 1340 m, near Kopitoto Peak, beech wood (leg. S. Lazarov): 5.VI.2000, 1 ♂ • [E3.02], soil traps: 1.VII–1.VIII.1999, 1 ♂. Westpalaeartic species, known from Southern Europe, Macaronesia, Dagestan (Caucasus) and Asia (Israel, Iran). Reported for the Balkan Peninsula from Bulgaria under the synonym *Megaselia insecta* Schmitz, 1953 (Schmitz, 1953a).

** 134. *Megaselia palmeni* (Becker, 1901) – Material examined: [E2.01], tree traps: 1.VI–1.VII.1999, 1 ♂ • 1840 m, near Aleko Chalet, spruce wood (leg. V. Beschovski): 10.VIII.1984, 2 ♂♂ • [W3.04] soil traps: 3.VII–7.VIII.1999, 2 ♂♂. European species. New region: Balkan Peninsula – Bulgaria.

** 135. *Megaselia pectinifera* Schmitz, 1926 – Material examined: [E3.02], soil traps: 1.X–1.XI.1998, 1 ♂. European species; till now known only from the Alps (Austria and Switzerland). New region: Balkan Peninsula – Bulgaria.

136. *Megaselia pectoralis* (Wood, 1910) – Material examined: [E1.05], tree traps: 1.VII–1.VIII.1999, 1 ♂ • [N1.05] Malaise trap: 12–14.VI.1998, 1 ♂ • [E3.02]: 1.VIII–1.IX.1998, 1 ♂, tree traps; 1.IX–1.X.1998, 1 ♂, soil traps; 1.VI–1.VII.1999, 2 ♂♂, soil traps • [W3.04] soil traps: 3.VII–7.VIII.1999, 2 ♂♂ • [S4.01]: 6.VII–7.VIII.1999, 3 ♂♂ • [W3.05] soil traps: 3.VII–7.VIII.1999, 2 ♂♂; 7.VIII–6.IX.1999, 1 ♂, 1 ♀ • [E3.04] soil traps: 1.VII–1.VIII.1999, 2 ♂♂; 1.VIII–1.IX.1999, 5 ♂♂; 1.IX–1.X.1999, 1 ♂. European species, for the Balkan Peninsula known from Montenegro (Langourov, 2004a). Other localities in Bulgaria: Sofia Plain (Langourov, 2004b) and Western Rhodope Mts (Langourov, 2010).

** 137. *Megaselia pectorella* Schmitz, 1929 – Material examined: [E2.01], tree traps: 1.VII–1.VIII.1999, 2 ♂♂. European species, known till now from Austria, Germany, Poland and Norway. New region: Balkan Peninsula – Bulgaria.

** 138. *Megaselia perfusca* Schmitz, 1935 – Material examined: [E2.01], soil traps: 1.VII–1.VIII.1999, 1 ♂ • [W3.05] soil traps: 7.VIII–6.IX.1999, 1 ♂ • [E3.04] soil traps: 1.VII–1.VIII.1999, 2 ♂♂. European; known from Austria, Germany, Poland and Czech Republic. New region: Balkan Peninsula – Bulgaria.

* 139. *Megaselia piliventris* Schmitz, 1937 – Material examined: [N1.05] Malaise trap: 12–14.VI.1998, 1 ♂ • [E2.01], tree traps: 1.V–1.VI.1999, 32 ♂♂; 1.VII–1.VIII.1999, 2 ♂♂ • [N2.03]: 31.V.1998, 1 ♂ • 1840 m, near Aleko Chalet, spruce wood (leg. V. Beschovski): 10.VIII.1984, 1 ♂ • [N3.01]: 3.IX.1992, 1 ♂ • [E3.02], tree traps: 1.V–1.VI.1999, 1 ♂. Westpalaearctic species, known from Europe and Asia (Yemen). Reported for the Balkan Peninsula from North Macedonia (Coe, 1956; Langourov, 1999 as *M. cirri-ventris* Schmitz, 1929).

140. *Megaselia pleuralis* (Wood, 1909) – Material examined: [S1.01] Malaise trap: 18–28.VIII.1998, 5 ♂♂; 28.VIII–4.IX.1998, 2 ♂♂; 900 m, near Bosnek Village, near Popov Izvor Karst spring, MSS traps: 6.VI–2.X.2013, 1 ♂; 910 m, near Bosnek Village, Popov Izvor Cave, soil traps: 2.X–2.XI.2013, 2 ♀♀; 954 m, near Bosnek Village, near Akademik Cave, MSS traps: 6.VI–2.X.2013, 2 ♀♀ • 1000 m, above Bistritsa village, *Formica pratensis* Retzius, 1783 nest

(leg. A. Lapeva): 14.XI.1997, 1 ♀ • [E1.05]: 1.VIII–1.IX.1998, 12 ♀♀, tree traps; 40 ♀♀, soil traps; 1.IX–1.X.1998, 3 ♀♀, tree traps; 1.VII–1.VIII.1999, 6 ♀♀, soil traps; 1.VIII–1.IX.1999, 6 ♀♀, soil traps; 1.IX–1.X.1999, 1 ♀, tree traps; 1 ♂, soil traps • [N1.06]: 1.VII–1.VIII.1998, 3 ♂♂, 27 ♀♀, soil traps; 2 ♀♀, tree traps; 1.VIII–1.IX.1998, 2 ♂♂, 11 ♀♀, soil traps; 2 ♂♂, 2 ♀♀, tree traps; 1.IX–1.X.1998, 2 ♂♂, 1 ♀, tree traps; 1.V–1.VI.1999, 2 ♂♂, soil traps; 1.VIII–1.IX.1999, 1 ♂, soil traps; 1.IX–1.X.1999, 1 ♂, soil traps • [E2.01]: 1.VIII–1.IX.1998, 21 ♀♀, tree traps; 2 ♂♂, 5 ♀♀, soil traps; 1.IX–1.X.1998, 1 ♂, 1 ♀, tree traps; 1.VII–1.VIII.1999, 2 ♂♂, tree traps; 1.VIII–1.IX.1999, 1 ♂, tree traps; 1.IX–1.X.1999, 1 ♂, 1 ♀, soil traps • 1750 m, near Kumata Chalet, spruce wood (leg. T. Ljubomirov): 22.VII.1997, 1 ♂ • 1840 m, near Aleko Chalet, spruce wood (leg. V. Beschovski): 10.VIII.1984, 1 ♂ • [W3.01]: 2.VI.1996, 1 ♂ • [E3.02]: 1.VIII–1.IX.1998, 4 ♂♂, 2 ♀♀, soil traps; 1.IX–1.X.1998, 1 ♂, soil traps; 1.V–1.VI.1999, 1 ♂, soil traps; 1.VI–1.VII.1999, 1 ♂, 1 ♀, tree traps; 1 ♀, soil traps; 1.VII–1.VIII.1999, 4 ♂♂, 2 ♀♀, soil traps. Subcosmopolitan species with Holarctic origin, widespread in the country (Czerny, 1930; Langourov, 2001, 2004c, 2010). For the Balkan Peninsula also known from North Macedonia (Coe, 1956; Langourov, 1999), Croatia, Bosnia-Herzegovina (Schmitz, 1919; Schmitz, 1928; Schmitz, 1953; Schmitz, 1957) and Montenegro (Langourov, 2004a).

141. *Megaselia plurispinulosa* (Zetterstedt, 1860) – Material examined: [N1.01] Malaise trap: 10–18.V.1997, 2 ♂♂, 1 ♀ • [S1.01] Malaise trap: 18–28.VIII.1998, 1 ♂; 28.VIII–4.IX.1998, 1 ♂ • [S2.01]: 31.VII–18.VIII.2000, 8 ♂♂; 18.VIII–1.IX.2000, 5 ♂♂. Palaearctic species, known from Europe, Macaronesia and Asia (Turkey, Iran, China). For the Balkan Peninsula also known from Greece, Slovenia, Italy (Schmitz, 1924, Schmitz, 1928) and North Macedonia (Coe, 1956; Langourov, 1991). In Bulgaria: Sofia Plain (Langourov, 2004b).

142. *Megaselia posticata* (Strobl, 1898) – Material examined: [N1.01] Malaise trap: 10–18.V.1997, 1 ♂; 900 m, near Bosnek Village, near Popov Izvor Karst spring, MSS traps: 6.VI–2.X.2013, 1 ♂, 3 ♀♀; 1118 m, 992 m, near Bosnek Village, near Duhlata Cave, MSS traps: 18.IV–16.VI.2007, 2 ♂♂. Westpalaearctic species, described from Croatia – Dubrovnik (Strobl, 1898); also known from Bosnia-Herzegovina, Slovenia (Schmitz, 1928). Other localities in Bulgaria: southern part of Vitosha Mt (Langourov et al., 2014).

143. *Megaselia producta* (Schmitz, 1921) – Material examined: 1840 m, near Aleko Chalet, spruce wood (leg. V. Beschovski): 10.VIII.1984, 2 ♂♂ • [N3.02]: 6.VIII–8.IX.1999, 1 ♂ • [E3.02]: 1.VIII–1.IX.1999, 1 ♂, tree traps; 1 ♂, soil traps • [E3.04] soil traps: 1.X–1.XI.1999, 1 ♂, 1 ♀. Westernpalearctic species, known from Europe and Asia (Iran). Other localities in Bulgaria: Eastern Rhodope Mountains (Langourov, 2004b) and Western Rhodope Mts (Langourov, 2010).

144. *Megaselia propinqua* (Wood, 1909) – Material examined: [E1.05] soil traps: 1.VIII–1.IX.1999, 2 ♂♂ • [N1.06]: 1.VII–1.VIII.1998, 1 ♂, soil traps; 1.V–1.VI.1999, 1 ♂, soil traps; 1.VI–1.VII.1999, 2 ♂♂, tree traps; 1.IX–1.X.1999, 1 ♂, soil traps • [E2.01], soil traps: 1.IX–1.X.1999, 1 ♂ • [W3.02] soil traps: 3.VII–7.VIII.1999, 1 ♂ • [E3.04] soil traps: 1.VII–1.VIII.1999, 1 ♂. European; for the Balkan Peninsula known from Serbia (Schmitz, 1924). Other localities in Bulgaria: W Stara Planina (Schmitz, 1953).

** 145. *Megaselia protarsalis* Schmitz, 1927 – Material examined: [N1.06] soil traps: 1.VII–1.VIII.1998, 1 ♂; 1.VIII–1.IX.1999, 4 ♂♂. Palearctic; from Middle Europe and Asia (Russian Far East). New region: Balkan Peninsula – Bulgaria.

* 146. *Megaselia pseudogiraudii* (Schmitz, 1920) – Material examined: [S2.01]: 23–30.V.2000, 1 ♂ • [E1.05], tree traps: 1.VIII–1.IX.1998, 1 ♀. Euro-Mediterranean species, for the Balkan Peninsula known from Croatia (Schmitz, 1928).

147. *Megaselia pumila* (Meigen, 1830) – Material examined: 1100 m, above Zhelezmitsa, mixed wood (leg. B. Dimitrova): 27.V.1983, 1 ♂ • [N1.05] Malaise trap: 12–14.VI.1998, 2 ♂♂ • [N1.06] soil traps: 1.VII–1.VIII.1998, 1 ♂ • [N1.07]: 20.VIII.1992, 1 ♀ • [E2.01]: 21.V.1997, 1 ♂, 1 ♀, in copula; 1.VIII–1.IX.1999, 1 ♂, tree traps; 1 ♂, soil traps • [E2.03]: 20.VIII.1992, 1 ♀ • [N3.02]: 12.VI–4.VII.1999, 1 ♂ • 1860 m, Torfeno Branishte reserve – Kapaklivets place, peatbog in subalpine zone: 28.VI.1993, 1 ♂ • [E3.02]: 1.VII–1.VIII.1999, 2 ♂♂, tree traps; 1.VIII–1.IX.1999, 1 ♂, 1 ♀, tree traps; 1 ♂, soil traps • [W3.02] soil traps: 5.VI–3.VII.1999, 1 ♂, 1 ♀. Palearctic; known from Europe, North Africa (Tunisia) and Asia (Israel, Russian Far East). Balkan Peninsula – Bosnia-Herzegovina (Strobl, 1898: as *Phora pulicaria* var. *pumila*), Croatia (Strobl, 1902: as *Phora pulicaria* var. *pumila*; Schmitz, 1924: as *Aphiochaeta atripes* Brues), Italy (Schmitz, 1928), North Macedonia (Langourov, 1999), Montenegro (Langourov, 2004a). Other localities in Bulgaria: Kresna

Gorge (Langourov & Sakalian, 2001) and Western Rhodope Mts (Langourov, 2010).

148. *Megaselia pusilla* (Meigen, 1830) – Material examined: [N1.01] Malaise trap: 10–18.V.1997, 3 ♂♂ • [S1.01] Malaise trap: 18–28.VIII.1998, 165 ♂♂; 28.VIII–4.IX.1998, 12 ♂♂; 2–31.X.1998, 1 ♂ • 1100 m, above Zhelezmitsa Village, coniferous plantation (leg.V. Beschovski): 18.V.1982, 1 ♂ • [N1.05] 1150 m: 21.VII.1992, 1 ♂ • [N1.05] Malaise trap: 5–12.VI.1998, 1 ♂ • [N1.06]: 1.VII–1.VIII.1998, 3 ♂♂, 3 ♀♀, soil traps; 15.IV–1.V.1999, 1 ♂, tree traps; 1.V–1.VI.1999, 1 ♂, soil traps; 1.VI–1.VII.1999, 1 ♂, soil traps • 1118 m, near Bosnek Village, Zhivata Voda Cave, 27.XI.2002, 3 ♀♀; [E3.02]: 1.V–1.VI.1999, 2 ♂♂, tree traps; 2 ♂♂, soil traps; 1.VI–1.VII.1999, 1 ♂, tree traps; 17 ♂♂, soil traps; 1.VII–1.VIII.1999, 4 ♂♂, tree traps • [N3.03] soil traps: 6.VIII–8.IX.1999, 1 ♂ • [E3.04] soil traps: 15.V–1.VI.1999, 1 ♂, 1 ♀. Holarctic species, known from Europe, Asia (China) and North America. For the Balkan Peninsula known from Slovenia (Schmitz, 1928) and Serbia (Coe, 1956). Other localities in Bulgaria: Kresna Gorge (Langourov & Sakalian, 2001), Eastern Rhodope Mts (Langourov, 2004b), Western Rhodope Mts (Langourov, 2010), southern part of Vitosha Mt (Langourov et al., 2014).

* 149. *Megaselia pygmaea* (Zetterstedt, 1848) – Material examined: [E1.01]: 15.IV.2000, 1 ♂ • [E1.05], tree traps: 1.VIII–1.IX.1998, 1 ♀. European species, on the Balkan Peninsula known from Serbia and Slovenia (Schmitz, 1924; Schmitz, 1928).

** 150. *Megaselia robusta* Schmitz, 1928 – Material examined: [E3.02], tree traps: 1.V–1.VI.1999, 1 ♂. Holarctic; known from North Europe and North America. New region: Balkan Peninsula – Bulgaria.

151. *Megaselia rubella* (Schmitz, 1920) – Material examined: [N1.05] Malaise trap: 3–8.VII.1998, 1 ♂. European species. Other localities in Bulgaria: Western Rhodope Mts (Langourov, 2010).

151. *Megaselia ruficornis* (Meigen, 1830) – Material examined: [N1.01] Malaise trap: 10–18.V.1997, 1 ♂ • [S1.01] Malaise trap: 18–28.VIII.1998, 2 ♂♂, 1 ♀; 1120 m, above Bosnek Village, on the road to Chui-petlyovo, scree in mixed wood, MSS traps: 6.VI–2.X.2013, 3 ♂♂ • [E1.05], tree traps: 1.VIII–1.IX.1998, 1 ♀. Holarctic species, known from Europe, Macaronesia, Asia (Russian Far East) and North America. For the Balkan Peninsula is known from Croatia (Langhoffer, 1919; Schmitz, 1924; Coe, 1956) and Montenegro (Langourov, 2004a). Other localities in Bulgaria: W Rhodope Mts (Langourov, 2010).

152. *Megaselia rufipes* (Meigen, 1804) – Material examined: [N1.01] Malaise trap: 10–18.V.1997, 1 ♂ • [S1.01] Malaise trap: 4–10.VIII.1998, 2 ♂♂; 18–28.VIII.1998, 2 ♂♂; 2–31.X.1998, 1 ♂. Cosmopolitan; widespread in the country. Balkan Peninsula – Italy (Funk & Graffe, 1895; Schmitz, 1919), Bosnia-Herzegovina (Strobl, 1900; Bezzi, 1911; Schmitz, 1919; Schmitz, 1928), Croatia (Strobl, 1902; Schmitz, 1919; Langhoffer, 1919; Schmitz, 1928; Coe, 1956), Montenegro (Schmitz, 1919), Greece – Corfu Island (Schmitz, 1924), North Macedonia (Langourov, 1999), Romania (Langourov, 2001).

** 153. *Megaselia rupestris* Schmitz, 1934 – Material examined: [E1.05] soil traps: 1.IX–1.X.1998, 3 ♂♂. European species, known till now from Austria, Great Britain, Czech Republic and Spain. New region: Balkan Peninsula – Bulgaria.

154. *Megaselia scalaris* (Loew, 1866) – Material examined: 900 m, near Bosnek Village, near Popov Izvor Karst spring, MSS traps: 6.VI–2.X.2013, 7 ♂♂, 1 ♀; 2.X–2.XI.2013, 1 ♂. Cosmopolitan; the only species of scuttle fly reported from Antarctica. Balkan Peninsula – Greece and Serbia (Langourov, 2004b). In Bulgaria: Sofia Plain (Langourov, 2004b).

155. *Megaselia scutellaris* (Wood, 1909) – Material examined: [S1.01] Malaise trap: 2–31.X.1998, 1 ♂ • [E1.04]: 3.IX.1992, 1 ♂ • [S2.01]: 16–23.V.2000, 1 ♂; 8–31.X.2000, 2 ♂♂ • [E1.05]: 1.VIII–1.IX.1998, 1 ♂, tree traps; 1.IX–1.X.1998, 1 ♂, 1 ♀, tree traps; 2 ♂♂, soil traps; 1.V–1.VI.1999, 1 ♀, tree traps; 1.VII–1.VIII.1999, 1 ♂, 2 ♀♀, soil traps; 1.VIII–1.IX.1999, 4 ♂♂, 1 ♀, tree traps; 1.IX–1.X.1999, 5 ♀♀, soil traps; 1.X–1.XI.1999, 4 ♀♀, soil traps • [N1.06] soil traps: 1.VII–1.VIII.1999, 1 ♂ • [E2.01], soil traps: 1.VIII–1.IX.1998, 1 ♂; 1.IX–1.X.1999, 1 ♂; 1.X–1.XI.1999, 1 ♂ • [N3.02]: 8.IX–5.X.1999, 1 ♂ • [E3.02], soil traps: 1.VII–1.VIII.1999, 1 ♂; 1.IX–1.X.1999, 11 ♂♂, 2 ♀♀; 1.X–1.XI.1999, 7 ♂♂, 1 ♀ • [E3.04] soil traps: 1.VII–1.VIII.1999, 1 ♂; 1.IX–1.X.1999, 1 ♂. European; Balkan Peninsula – Bosnia-Herzegovina (Schmitz, 1919), Croatia (Schmitz, 1924), Albania, Slovenia (Schmitz, 1928). In Bulgaria: Eastern Rhodope Mts (Langourov, 2004b) and Western Rhodope Mts (Langourov, 2010).

** 156. *Megaselia sepulchralis* (Lundbeck, 1920) – Material examined: [E2.01], tree traps: 1.VII–1.VIII.1998, 1 ♂. Palearctic species, known from North and Middle Europe and Asia (Russian Far East). New region: Balkan Peninsula – Bulgaria.

** 157. *Megaselia sericata* Schmitz, 1935 – Material examined: [N1.06], tree traps: 15.IV–1.V.1999, 1 ♂. European; known till now only from Austria and Germany. New region: Balkan Peninsula – Bulgaria.

** 158. *Megaselia setulipalpis* Schmitz, 1938 – Material examined: [E1.05], tree traps: 1.VII–1.VIII.1998, 1 ♂. European species, known from North and Middle Europe. New region: Balkan Peninsula – Bulgaria.

* 159. *Megaselia simplex* (Wood, 1910) – Material examined: [E1.03]: 15.IV.2000, 1 ♂. European species. On the Balkan Peninsula also known from Montenegro (Langourov, 2004a).

160. *Megaselia simulans* (Wood, 1912) – Material examined: [N1.06] soil traps: 1.VIII–1.IX.1999, 1 ♂. Westernpalearctic species, known from Europe and Asia (Eastern Siberia). For the Balkan Peninsula also known from Croatia (Coe, 1956). Other localities in Bulgaria: Western Rhodope Mts (Langourov, 2010).

161. *Megaselia sordida* (Zetterstedt, 1838) – Material examined: 2226 m, Skoparnik Peak, subalpine zone (leg. V. Beschovski): 21.VIII.1981, 2 ♂♂. Holarctic species, known from Europe, Asia (Siberia, Russian Far East) and North America. Other localities in Bulgaria: Western Rhodope Mts (Langourov, 2010).

** 162. *Megaselia spinata* (Wood, 1910) – Material examined: [N1.06], tree traps: 1.VIII–1.IX.1999, 1 ♂. European species, known till now from Austria and Great Britain. New region: Balkan Peninsula – Bulgaria.

* 163. *Megaselia spinigera* (Wood, 1908) – Material examined: [N1.01] Malaise trap: 12–17.V.1998, 1 ♂ • [N1.06] soil traps: 1.V–1.VI.1999, 1 ♂ • [E3.02]: 1.VII–1.VIII.1998, 1 ♂, tree traps; 1.V–1.VI.1999, 1 ♂, soil traps. European species. For the Balkan Peninsula also known from Croatia (Schmitz, 1924).

164. *Megaselia stichata* (Lundbeck, 1920) – Material examined: [E1.05], tree traps: 1.VI–1.VII.1999, 1 ♂. Westpalearctic species, known from Europe, Macaronesia and Asia (Israel, Iran). For the Balkan Peninsula also known from Montenegro (Langourov, 2004a). Other localities in Bulgaria: Sofia Plain (Langourov, 2004b).

* 165. *Megaselia styloprocta* (Schmitz, 1921) – Material examined: [E1.03]: 15.IV.2000, 1 ♂ • [N1.05] Malaise trap: 29.V–5.VI.1998, 1 ♂; 5–12.VI.1998, 3 ♂♂ • [N1.06] soil traps: 1.V–1.VI.1999, 1 ♂. Westpalearctic species, known from Europe and Asia (Iran). For the Balkan Peninsula also known from Slovenia (Schmitz, 1928).

** 166. *Megaselia subconvexa* (Lundbeck, 1920) – Material examined: [S1.01] Malaise trap: 18–28.VIII.1998, 1 ♂ • [N1.06], tree traps: 1.VI–1.VII.1998, 1 ♂. European species, known till now from Austria, Great Britain, Denmark and Netherlands. New region: Balkan Peninsula – Bulgaria.

* 167. *Megaselia subpleuralis* (Wood, 1909) – Material examined: [E1.05] soil traps: 1.VII–1.VIII.1999, 1 ♂ • [E2.01]: 28.V.1998, 1 ♂. Holarctic species, known from Europe, Macaronesia, Asia (Israel) and North America. For the Balkan Peninsula also known from Montenegro (Langourov, 2004a). Other localities in Bulgaria: Western Rhodope Mts (Langourov, 2010).

168. *Megaselia subtumida* (Wood, 1909) – Material examined: [N1.06] soil traps: 1.VII–1.VIII.1998, 1 ♀; 1.VI–1.VII.1999, 1 ♀; 900 m, near Bosnek Village, near Popov Izvor Karst spring, MSS traps: 2.X–2.XI.2013, 1 ♂. European species. Other localities in Bulgaria: W Rhodope Mts (Langourov, 2010) and southern part of Vitosha Mt (Langourov et al., 2014).

169. *Megaselia sylvatica* (Wood, 1910) – Material examined: [N1.05] Malaise trap: 11–15.VII.1998, 1 ♂ • [N1.06] soil traps: 1.IX–1.X.1999, 1 ♂. European species. For the Balkan Peninsula also known from Montenegro (Langourov, 2004a). Other localities in Bulgaria: North Black Sea Coast (Schmitz, 1953).

** 170. *Megaselia tama* (Schmitz, 1926) – Material examined: [N1.01] Malaise trap: 5–12.V.1998, 1 ♂ • [S1.01] Malaise trap: 10–18.VIII.1998, 1 ♂. Westpalaearctic species, known from Europe and Asia (Iran). New region: Balkan Peninsula – Bulgaria.

* 171. *Megaselia tarsalis* (Wood, 1910) – Material examined: [N1.01] Malaise trap: 10–18.V.1997, 2 ♂♂ • [E1.05]: 1.VII–1.VIII.1999, 1 ♂, tree traps; 1.VIII–1.IX.1999, 1 ♂, tree traps; 1.X–1.XI.1999, 1 ♂, tree traps; 1 ♂, soil traps • [N1.06]: 2.X.1999, 1 ♂; 1.VIII–1.IX.1998, 1 ♂, soil traps; 1.IX–1.X.1998, 1 ♂, soil traps; 1.X–1.XI.1998, 1 ♂, soil traps; 1.VI–1.VII.1999, 1 ♂, soil traps • [E3.04] soil traps: 1.VI–1.VII.1999, 3 ♂♂, 1 ♀. European; for the Balkan Peninsula is known from Greece (Schmitz, 1924), North Macedonia, Croatia (Coe, 1956; Langourov, 1999) and Montenegro (Langourov, 2004a).

172. *Megaselia tarsella* (Lundbeck, 1921) – Material examined: [S1.01] Malaise trap: 4–10.VIII.1998, 1 ♂ • [N1.06] soil traps: 1.VIII–1.IX.1998, 1 ♂; 1.V–1.VI.1999, 3 ♂♂, 2 ♀♀ • 1840 m, near Aleko Chalet, spruce wood: 12.IX.1999, 1 ♂ – feeding on sugar syrup • [E3.02], soil traps: 1.VII–1.VIII.1999, 1 ♂ • [E3.04] soil traps: 1.VI–1.VII.1999, 20 ♂♂,

5 ♀♀; 1.VII–1.VIII.1999, 20 ♂♂, 9 ♀♀. Palaearctic species, known from Europe and Asia (Russian Far East). Other localities in Bulgaria: Sofia Plain (Langourov, 2004b).

** 173. *Megaselia tarsicia* Schmitz, 1926 – Material examined: [E1.05] soil traps: 1.IX–1.X.1998, 1 ♂ • [E2.01]: 1.VII–1.VIII.1998, 4 ♂♂, 5 ♀♀, tree traps; 7 ♂♂, 1 ♀, soil traps; 1.VIII–1.IX.1998, 4 ♂♂, 9 ♀♀, tree traps; 10 ♂♂, 7 ♀♀, soil traps; 1.IX–1.X.1998, 1 ♂, tree traps; 1.VIII–1.IX.1999, 6 ♂♂, 3 ♀♀, tree traps; 3 ♂♂, soil traps • [E3.02]: 1.VII–1.VIII.1998, 164 ♂♂, 22 ♀♀, tree traps; 1.VIII–1.IX.1998, 17 ♂♂, 5 ♀♀, tree traps; 1.IX–1.X.1998, 1 ♂, tree traps; 1.VI–1.VII.1999, 67 ♂♂, 10 ♀♀, tree traps; 1.VII–1.VIII.1999, 20 ♂♂, tree traps; 116 ♂♂, 8 ♀♀, soil traps; 1.VIII–1.IX.1999, 2 ♂♂, 3 ♀♀, tree traps; 3 ♂♂, 2 ♀♀, soil traps • [W3.05] soil traps: 3.VII–7.VIII.1999, 1 ♂. Palaearctic species, known from Europe and Asia (Russian Far East). New region: Balkan Peninsula – Bulgaria.

174. *Megaselia tenebricola* Schmitz, 1934 – Material examined: 1006 m, near Bosnek Village, near Duhlata Cave, MSS traps: 2.X–2.XI.2013, 1 ♂; 1120 m, above Bosnek Village, on the road to Chuipetlyovo, scree in mixed wood, MSS traps: 6.VI–2.X.2013, 1 ♂. European species. Other localities in Bulgaria: Fore-Balkan Mts and Vitosha (Langourov, 2001; Langourov et al., 2014).

175. *Megaselia trichorrhoea* (Schmitz, 1921) – Material examined: [N1.06] soil traps: 1.VII–1.VIII.1998, 3 ♂♂. European species. For the Balkan Peninsula also known from Croatia, North Macedonia (Coe, 1956) and Bulgaria (Disney, 1991).

* 176. *Megaselia tumida* (Wood, 1909) – Material examined: [E1.05] soil traps: 1.IX–1.X.1998, 1 ♀. Westpalaearctic species, known from Europe and North Africa (Tunisia). For the Balkan Peninsula also known from Bosnia-Herzegovina (Schmitz, 1919) and Croatia (Coe, 1956).

** 177. *Megaselia uliginosa* (Wood, 1909) – Material examined: [E1.05], tree traps: 1.VIII–1.IX.1999, 1 ♂. European species, known from Middle Europe. New region: Balkan Peninsula – Bulgaria.

178. *Megaselia unicolor* (Schmitz, 1919) – Material examined: [E1.05], tree traps: 1.VIII–1.IX.1998, 1 ♂ • [E2.01]: 1.VII–1.VIII.1998, 1 ♂, soil traps; 1.VIII–1.IX.1999, 1 ♂, tree traps • [E3.02]: 1.VIII–1.IX.1998, 9 ♂♂, 1 ♀, tree traps; 2 ♀♀, soil traps; 1.IX–1.X.1998, 1 ♂, tree traps; 1 ♀, soil traps; 1.VII–1.VIII.1999, 49 ♂♂, numerous ♀♀, tree traps;

4 ♂♂, 12 ♀♀, soil traps; 1.VIII–1.IX.1999, 16 ♂♂, tree traps; 5 ♂♂, 3 ♀♀, soil traps • [E3.04]: 5.VIII.1999, 10 ♂♂, on racemes of *Angelica sylvestris* L. • [W3.03] soil traps: 3.VII–7.VIII.1999, 1 ♂ • [W3.05] soil traps: 3.VII–7.VIII.1999, 3 ♂♂ • [E3.04] soil traps: 1.VIII–1.IX.1998, 1 ♂, 3 ♀♀; 1.VII–1.VIII.1999, 2 ♂♂; 1.VIII–1.IX.1999, 2 ♂♂, 2 ♀♀; 1.XI.1999–1.V.2000, 1 ♂. Palearctic species, known from Europe and Asia (China). Other localities in Bulgaria: Eastern Rhodope Mts (Langourov, 2004c).

* 179. *Megaselia variana* Schmitz, 1926 – Material examined: [E1.05] soil traps: 1.VII–1.VIII.1999, 1 ♂; 1.IX–1.X.1999, 1 ♂ • [N1.05] Malaise trap: 12–14.VI.1998, 1 ♂. European species. For the Balkan Peninsula known from Croatia (Schmitz, 1924).

180. *Megaselia verna* Schmitz, 1932 – Material examined: [E3.02], tree traps: 1.V–1.VI.1999, 3 ♂♂. Euro-Mediterranean species. Other localities in Bulgaria: Kresna Gorge (Langourov & Sakalian, 2001).

181. *Megaselia vernalis* (Wood, 1909) – Material examined: [W1.01] tree traps: 8–14.VII.1998, 1 ♂ • [E1.01]: 15.IV.2000, 1 ♂ • [E1.05] soil traps: 1.XI.1998–1.V.1999, 1 ♂, 1 ♀ • [N1.06] soil traps: 15.IV–1.V.1999, 8 ♂♂, 2 ♀♀; 1.V–1.VI.1999, 6 ♂♂, 3 ♀♀; 1.VI–1.VII.1999, 2 ♂♂, 1 ♀ • [E2.01], tree traps: 1.VIII–1.IX.1999, 1 ♂ • [E3.04] soil traps: 15.V–1.VI.1999, 1 ♂. European species. Other localities in Bulgaria: Eastern Rhodope Mts (Langourov, 2004c).

182. *Megaselia verralli* (Wood, 1910) – Material examined: [S1.01] Malaise trap: 4–10.VIII.1998, 4 ♂♂; 18–28.VIII.1998, 6 ♂♂. Westpalaeartic species, known from Europe, Macaronesia and Asia (Israel, Iran). For the Balkan Peninsula also known from Slovenia, Greece (the island of Crete) (Schmitz, 1928) and North Macedonia (Coe, 1956). Other localities in Bulgaria: Sofia Plain, Sofia (Schmitz, 1953).

183. *Megaselia vestita* (Wood, 1914) – Material examined: [E1.03]: 15.IV.2000, 1 ♂. European species. In Bulgaria: W Rhodope Mts (Langourov, 2010).

** 184. *Megaselia woodi* (Lundbeck, 1922) – Material examined: [S2.01]: 8–31.X.2000, 1 ♂ • [E1.05]: 1.X–1.XI.1998, 1 ♂, 1 ♀, tree traps; 1.X–1.XI.1999, 1 ♀, soil traps • between [E1.05] to [E1.06]: 17.X.1992, 3 ♂♂ • [N1.06] soil traps: 1.IX–1.X.1998, 1 ♂, 1 ♀ • between [N1.07] to [N2.01]: 27.VIII.1992, 1 ♂ • [E2.01], tree traps: 1.IX–1.X.1998, 3 ♂♂, 4 ♀♀; 1.X–1.XI.1999, 1 ♂ • 1830 m, Bistrishko Branishte Reserve, near Fizkulturnik Chalet, subalpine zone (leg. V. Beschovski): 8.X.1981, 1 ♂ • [E3.02]: 1.IX–1.X.1998, 1 ♂, soil traps; 1.VIII–1.IX.1999,

6 ♂♂, tree traps; 1.IX–1.X.1999, 1 ♂, tree traps • [E3.03] soil traps: 8.IX–5.X.1999, 1 ♀ • [E3.04] soil traps: 1.VIII–1.IX.1998, 1 ♂; 1.IX–1.X.1998, 1 ♂; 1.VIII–1.IX.1999, 2 ♂♂; 1.IX–1.X.1999, 1 ♂. European. New region: Balkan Peninsula – Bulgaria.

185. *Megaselia xanthozona* (Strobl, 1892) – Material examined: [N1.01] Malaise trap: 10–18.V.1997, 1 ♂ • [S1.01] Malaise trap: 18–28.VIII.1998, 1 ♂; 28.VIII–4.IX.1998, 1 ♂ • [E3.01] soil traps: 6.VI–3.VII.1999, 1 ♂, 2 ♀♀ • [E3.02]: 1.VI–1.VII.1999, 1 ♂, soil traps; 1.VII–1.VIII.1999, 1 ♂, tree traps. Palearctic; for the Balkan Peninsula also known from North Macedonia (Langourov, 1999). In Bulgaria: W Rhodope Mts (Langourov, 2010).

* 186. *Menoziola schmitzi* (Menozzi, 1921) – Material examined: [N1.05] Malaise trap: 19–26.VI.1998, 1 ♂. Euro-Mediterranean species. For the Balkan Peninsula also known from Croatia (Schmitz, 1928).

187. *Phalacrotophora fasciata* (Fallen, 1823) – Material examined: [S1.01] Malaise trap: 4–10.VIII.1998, 1 ♂. Palearctic species, known from Europe and Asia (Turkey, Israel, Iran, China, Siberia, Russian Far East). For the Balkan Peninsula also known from Italy (Funk & Graffe, 1895). Other localities in Bulgaria: Sofia Plain (Langourov, 2004b).

** 188. *Plectanocnema nudipes* (Becker, 1901) – Material examined: [S1.01] Malaise trap: 3–17.IV.1999, 1 ♂. Holarctic species, known from Europe, Asia (Russian Far East) and North America. New region: Balkan Peninsula – Bulgaria.

** 189. *Tubicera lichtwardti* Schmitz, 1920 – Material examined: [S2.01]: 28.VI–15.VII.2000, 2 ♂♂. Mediterranean species, known until now from Spain, France, Hungary and Israel. New region: Balkan Peninsula – Bulgaria.

190. *Gymnophora arcuata* (Meigen, 1830) – Material examined: [S1.01] Malaise trap: 18–28.VIII.1998, 1 ♀; 25.IX–2.X.1998, 1 ♂; 900 m, near Bosnek Village, near Popov Izvor Karst spring, MSS traps: 6.VI–2.X.2013, 3 ♂♂, 1 ♀; 954 m, near Bosnek Village, near Akademik Cave, MSS traps: 6.VI–2.X.2013, 1 ♂. Westpalaeartic species, known from Europe and Asia (Israel, Iran). For the Balkan Peninsula also known from Italy (Funk & Graffe, 1895), Bosnia-Herzegovina (Strobl, 1898), Croatia (Strobl, 1902, Langhoffer, 1919), Greece (Disney, 1991), North Macedonia (Langourov, 1999) and Montenegro (Langourov, 2004a). Other localities in Bulgaria: southern part of Vitosha Mt (Langourov et al., 2014).

191. *Gymnophora integralis* Schmitz, 1920 – Material examined: [N1.01] Malaise trap: 10–18.V.1997, 2 ♂♂, 1 ♀ • [S1.01] Malaise trap: 2–31.X.1998, 1 ♂; 3–17.IV.1999, 3 ♂♂; 900 m, near Bosnek Village, near Popov Izvor Karst spring, MSS traps: 2.X–2.XI.2013, 1 ♂ • [E1.01]: 15.IV.2000, 1 ♂ • [E1.05]: 1.VI–1.VII.1998, 1 ♂, soil traps; 1.IX–1.X.1998, 1 ♀, tree traps; 1 ♀, soil traps; 1.X–1.XI.1998, 1 ♂, soil traps; 1.V–1.VI.1999, 1 ♂, tree traps; 2 ♂♂, soil traps; 1.IX–1.X.1999, 1 ♂, 3 ♀♀, soil traps • [N1.05] Malaise trap: 26.VI–3.VII.1998, 1 ♂, 1 ♀ • [N1.06] soil traps: 1.IX–1.X.1998, 1 ♂; 15.IV–1.V.1999, 1 ♂, 1 ♀; 1.V–1.VI.1999, 1 ♂; 1.VI–1.VII.1999, 2 ♂♂; 1.IX–1.X.1999, 2 ♀♀; 1.X–1.XI.1999, 1 ♂. Palaearctic species, known from Europe and Asia (Israel, Japan, Russian Far East). For the Balkan Peninsula it is known from Croatia (Schmitz, 1928). Other localities in Bulgaria: Eastern Rhodope Mts (Langourov, 2004c) and southern part of Vitosha Mt (Langourov et al., 2014).

** 192. *Gymnophora quartomollis* Schmitz, 1920 – Material examined: [E1.05]: 1.VI–1.VII.1999, 1 ♂, 1 ♀, soil traps; 1.VII–1.VIII.1999, 1 ♂, tree traps; 7 ♂♂, 3 ♀♀, soil traps; 1.VIII–1.IX.1999, 1 ♀, soil traps • [N1.06]: 1.VIII–1.IX.1998, 2 ♀♀, soil traps; 1.VI–1.VII.1999, 1 ♀, soil traps; 1.VII–1.VIII.1999, 4 ♀♀, soil traps; 1.VIII–1.IX.1999, 1 ♂, 2 ♀♀, tree traps; 2 ♂♂, 2 ♀♀, soil traps • [E2.01], soil traps: 1.VIII–1.IX.1999, 1 ♂, 1 ♀. European species. New region: Balkan Peninsula – Bulgaria.

** 193. *Metopina braueri* (Strobl, 1880) – Material examined: [S1.01] Malaise trap: 4–10.VIII.1998, 3 ♂♂, 2 ♀♀; 10–22.VII.1999, 3 ♀♀. Westpalaearctic species, known from Europe and Asia (Israel). New region: Balkan Peninsula – Bulgaria.

** 194. *Metopina crassinervis* Schmitz, 1920 – Material examined: [S1.01] Malaise trap: 2–31.X.1998, 2 ♂♂. European; known from Great Britain, Germany, Switzerland, Slovakia and Netherlands. New region: Balkan Peninsula – Bulgaria.

195. *Metopina galeata* (Haliday, 1833) – Material examined: [S1.01] Malaise trap: 4–10.VIII.1998, 4 ♂♂, 5 ♀♀; 10–22.VII.1999, 5 ♀♀; 1006 m, near Bosnek Village, near Duhlata Cave, MSS traps: 6.VI–2.X.2013, 1 ♀. European species. For the Balkan Peninsula also known from Greece (Disney, 1991) and Montenegro (Langourov, 2004a). Published for the mountain by Langourov et al. (2014).

* 196. *Metopina heselhausi* Schmitz, 1914 – Material examined: [S1.01] Malaise trap: 4–10.VIII.1998, 18 ♂♂, 1 ♀ • [N1.06], tree traps: 1.VIII–1.IX.1999,

1 ♀ • [E3.02], tree traps: 1.VII–1.VIII.1999, 1 ♂. Westpalaearctic species, known also from the Afrotropical Region (Benin). For the Balkan Peninsula also known from Greece (Disney, 1991).

* 197. *Metopina oligoneura* (Mik, 1867) – Material examined: [S1.01] Malaise trap: 4–10.VIII.1998, 5 ♂♂; 10–22.VII.1999, 1 ♀ • [E1.05], tree traps: 1.IX–1.X.1998, 1 ♂ • [W3.03] soil traps: 3.VII–7.VIII.1999, 1 ♀. Westpalaearctic; known from Europe and Asia (Iran). For the Balkan Peninsula it is known from Montenegro (Langourov, 2004a).

* 198. *Metopina perpusilla* (Six, 1878) – Material examined: [N1.02] Malaise trap: 10–17.VIII.1999, 2 ♀♀ • [S1.01] Malaise trap: 4–10.VIII.1998, 1 ♀. European species, for the Balkan Peninsula it is known from Croatia (Schmitz, 1928).

* 199. *Metopina pileata* Schmitz, 1936 – Material examined: [N1.02]: 27.X.1999, 1 ♂ • [N1.02] Malaise trap: 1–18.IX.1999, 3 ♀♀ • [S1.01] Malaise trap: 4–10.VIII.1998, 8 ♂♂; 10–22.VII.1999, 2 ♀♀ • [S2.01]: 31.VII–18.VIII.2000, 1 ♀ • [N1.06], tree traps: 1.IX–1.X.1999, 1 ♀. Westpalaearctic; known from Europe, North Africa (Algeria) and Asia (Israel). Balkan Peninsula – Greece (Disney, 1991).

** 200. *Metopina ulrichi* Disney, 1979 – Material examined: [S1.01] Malaise trap: 4–10.VIII.1998, 1 ♀; 10–22.VII.1999, 6 ♀♀. Westpalaearctic species, known from Europe and Asia (Israel). New region: Balkan Peninsula – Bulgaria.

201. *Beckerina umbrimargo* (Becker, 1901) – Material examined: [N1.01] Malaise trap: 10–18.V.1997, 4 ♂♂, 1 ♀; 22–28.IV.1998, 1 ♂, 2 ♀♀; 28.IV–1.V.1998, 2 ♂♂; 1–5.V.1998, 6 ♂♂, 1 ♀; 5–12.V.1998, 2 ♂♂, 1 ♀; 12–17.V.1998, 1 ♂. European species. Other localities in Bulgaria: Western Rhodope Mts (Langourov, 2010).

Discussion

Two hundred and one species, belonging to 19 genera as follows – *Aenigmatias* (2), *Anevrina* (4), *Beckerina* (1), *Borophaga* (1), *Chaetopleurophora* (4), *Conicera* (5), *Diplonevra* (6), *Gymnophora* (3), *Gymnoptera* (1), *Megaselia* (125), *Menozziola* (1), *Metopina* (8), *Peromittra* (2), *Phalacrotophora* (1), *Phora* (10), *Plectanocnema* (1), *Spiniphora* (4), *Triphleba* (21), *Tubicera* (1) – have been established on Vitosha during the investigation. *Gymnoptera*, *Peromittra*, *Plectanocnema* and *Tubicera* are recorded for the first time for

the Balkan Peninsula and *Menoziola* – for Bulgaria. Sixty-nine species are new for the Balkan Peninsula and additional 32 – for Bulgaria. For most of these species the Balkan Peninsula is the southernmost part of their known range. Of special interest among them are *Triphleba longifurcata*, *T. withersi* and *Megaselia abernethae*, known until now only from their type-localities. On the basis of the established number of species, it can be concluded that Vitosha is an area with a significant scuttle fly diversity.

Five plant species, belonging to four families, visited by the scuttle flies for additional nutrition were identified during the research. They are as follows: Iridaceae, *Crocus veluchensis* Herb. (*Triphleba intermedia* and *T. pachyneurella*); Salicaceae, *Salix caprea* L. (*Triphleba intermedia*); Apiaceae, *Angelica sylvestris* L. (*Megaselia aculeata*, *M. coei*, *M. unicolor*, *Phora stictica*, *Spiniphora jugorum*) and *Anthriscus nitida* (Wahlenb.) Garcke (*Phora tinctoria*); Asteraceae, *Petasites hybridus ochroleucus* (Boiss. & A. Huet) Šourek (*Conicera floricola*, *Megaselia angusta*). All the above mentioned species of scuttle flies (with the exception of *M. coei*) are recorded for the first time as flower visitors of these plants. Flower visiting by scuttle flies of family Iridaceae and three of the species (excluding *A. sylvestris* and *Salix caprea*) is recorded for the first time. For four scuttle fly species (*T. pachyneurella*, *Megaselia aculeata*, *M. unicolor* and *M. angusta*) anthophilia is recorded for the first time.

After the present investigation, the number of the established scuttle flies for Bulgaria increases to 231, while for the Balkan Peninsula it is 279 (Schmitz, 1924, 1928, 1953; Disney, 1991, 2003; Langourov, 1999, 2001, 2004a, 2004b, 2004c, 2010; Langourov & Sakalian, 2001; Langourov et al., 2014).

Acknowledgments

I would like to thank all my colleagues who kindly submitted the materials collected by them – O. Mikov, V. Beschovski, T. Ljubomirov, E. Manasieva, S. Lazarov, N. Simov, A. Lapeva, B. Dimitrova.

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